

POLITÉCNICA

ESCUELA TÉCNICA SUPERIOR DE INGENIEROS INDUSTRIALES
UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID

José Gutiérrez Abascal, 2. 28006 Madrid
Tel.: 91 336 3060
info.industriales@upm.es

www.industriales.upm.es

TRABAJO FIN DE MASTER

INTEGRATION OF A CGRA ACCELERATOR WITH A CVA6 RISC-V CORE FOR THE CLOUD-EDGE CONTINUUM

Juan Granja Garijo

05 TRABAJO FIN DE MASTER

INDUSTRIALES

SEPTIEMBRE 2024

Juan Granja Garijo

DIRECTOR DEL TRABAJO FIN DE MASTER:
Andrés Otero Marnotes

POLITÉCNICA

UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID
ESCUELA TÉCNICA SUPERIOR DE
INGENIEROS INDUSTRIALES

MASTER THESIS

INTEGRATION OF A CGRA
ACCELERATOR WITH A CVA6 RISC-V
CORE FOR THE CLOUD-EDGE
CONTINUUM

MASTER IN INDUSTRIAL ELECTRONICS

JUAN GRANJA GARIJO
MADRID, 2024

INTEGRATION OF A CGRA ACCELERATOR WITH A CVA6 RISC-V CORE FOR THE CLOUD-EDGE CONTINUUM

Author: Juan Granja Garijo

Supervisor: Andrés Otero Marnotes

Degree: Master in Industrial Electronics

Abstract

The computing continuum is a new paradigm that views the cloud, edge, and fog layers of the Internet of Things as part of a single space where computing tasks can be scheduled on various devices [1]. In this context, edge devices could benefit from application-class processors and reconfigurable accelerators to provide further adaptability and local processing capabilities.

This master's thesis has been elaborated at the Center for Industrial Electronics (CEI) of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM). It targets the development of adaptable edge nodes for the cloud-edge continuum, applying technologies related to *Coarse-Grain Reconfigurable Arrays* (CGRAs) and RISC-V processors. This work has been carried out in the context of the MYRTUS project [2], funded by the European Union with grant number 101135183.

More specifically, this master's thesis aims to integrate a CGRA accelerator previously developed at CEI [3] with an application-class RISC-V processor on a System on Chip (SoC) and evaluate its performance when accelerating a set of tasks. The resulting system will then serve as a starting point for developing an edge node for the cloud-edge continuum.

To do so, a state-of-the-art SoC platform with an application-grade RISC-V processor has been selected. An FPGA emulation of this platform is started on a development board available at CEI, and the hardware needed to integrate the CGRA is developed.

A kernel module is written so that the CGRA accelerator may be used from within a Linux user process. This allows to take advantage of the application-class processor, by running Linux, and of the hardware acceleration provided by the CGRA.

Finally, accelerator performance is evaluated both in bare-metal and Linux contexts, including a comparison with purely software solutions (i.e., without hardware acceleration).

Keywords: Internet of Things, Cloud-Edge Continuum, RISC-V, CGRA, System on Chip.

UNESCO Codes:

- 2203.07 Electronics - Integrated circuits
- 3304.06 Computer technology - Computer architecture
- 3304.11 Computer technology - Computing systems design

Resumen

El continuo *cloud-edge* es un nuevo paradigma que engloba las capas del Internet de las cosas: *cloud*, *edge* y *fog* en un único espacio, donde es posible distribuir tareas de cómputo entre los dispositivos disponibles [1]. En este ámbito resulta ventajoso dotar a los dispositivos del *edge* de procesadores de aplicaciones y de aceleradores reconfigurables, aumentando su capacidad de proceso y adaptación.

Este trabajo de fin de máster ha sido elaborado en el Centro de Electrónica Industrial (CEI) de la Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM). Su objetivo es el desarrollo de nodos adaptables para el continuo *cloud-edge*, empleando tecnologías relacionadas con los dispositivos reconfigurables de grano grueso (CGRA por sus siglas en inglés) y procesadores RISC-V. El trabajo se ha desarrollado en el contexto del proyecto MYRTUS [2], financiado por la Unión Europea, con número de subvención 101135183.

El presente trabajo aspira integrar un acelerador de tipo CGRA desarrollado previamente en el CEI [3] junto con un procesador de aplicaciones RISC-V, en un sistema en chip (*System on Chip*, SoC), y evaluar la aceleración proporcionada por el CGRA en una serie de tareas. El sistema resultante constituirá un punto de partida para el desarrollo de un nodo *edge* para el continuo *cloud-edge*.

Para llevar a cabo lo anterior, se selecciona de entre el estado del arte una plataforma para el desarrollo de SoCs portando un procesador de aplicaciones RISC-V. Una emulación en FPGA de esta plataforma se pone en marcha en una placa de desarrollo disponible en el CEI, y se realizan los desarrollos hardware necesarios para la integración del CGRA en dicha plataforma.

Además, se escribe un módulo para el núcleo de Linux que permite el uso del CGRA desde un proceso de usuario. Esto hace posible sacar partido al procesador de aplicaciones, capaz de correr Linux, y a la aceleración hardware proporcionada por el CGRA.

Por último, el rendimiento del acelerador se evalúa en un contexto sin sistema operativo (*bare-metal*) y en Linux. Los resultados se comparan con una solución puramente software, sin aceleración hardware.

Palabras clave: Internet de las cosas, Continuo cloud-edge, RISC-V, CGRA, Sistemas en Chip.

Códigos UNESCO:

- 2203.07 Electrónica - Circuitos integrados
- 3304.06 Tecnología de los ordenadores - Arquitectura de ordenadores
- 3304.11 Tecnología de los ordenadores - Diseño de sistemas de cálculo

List of Acronyms

AHB	Advanced High-performance Bus
ALU	Arithmetic-Logic Unit
AMBA	Advanced Micro-controller Bus Architecture.
APB	Advanced Peripheral Bus
APU	Application Processor Unit.
ASIC	Application-Specific Integrated Circuit.
AXI	Advanced Extensible Interface.
BRAM	Block Random Access Memory, as a resource inside an FPGA.
CEI	Center for Industrial Electronics / Centro de Electrónica Industrial.
CGRA	Coarse-Grain Reconfigurable Architecture.
CPU	Central Processing Unit.
CSR	Control-Status Register.
DMA	Direct Memory Access.
DRAM	Dynamic Random-Access Memory.
DSP	Digital Signal Processing.
ELF	Executable Linkable File.
FF	Flip-Flop
FIFO	First-In First-Out, as in a buffer.
FMC	FPGA Mezzanine Card.
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array.
FSBL	First-Stage Bootloader.
GCC	GNU Compiler Collection.
GDB	GNU Debugger.

GPIO	General-Purpose Input/Output.
GUI	Graphical User Interface.
HDL	Hardware Description Language, e.g., SystemVerilog or VHDL.
IC	Integrated Circuit.
ILA	Integrated Logic Analyzer (Xilinx).
IOCTL	Input Output ConTroL, commands part of the interface between a Linux user program and a device driver.
IoT	Internet of Things.
IP	Intellectual Property, e.g. an HDL module.
ISA	Instruction Set Architecture.
JTAG	Joint Test Action Group, a standard for on-chip instrumentation that defines a Test Access Port (TAP).
LUT	LookUp Table, as a resource inside an FPGA.
MCS	Micro Computer Set, an Intel hexadecimal file format. Used by Vivado for configuration memory contents.
MMU	Memory Management Unit.
NoC	Network on Chip.
PE	Processing Element (of a CGRA).
PMCA	Programmable Many-Core Accelerator.
RAM	Random-Access Memory.
ROM	Read Only Memory.
RTL	Register Transfer Level, for hardware description.
SoC	System on Chip.
SPI	Serial Peripheral Interface.
SPM	Scratch-Pad Memory.
SSBL	Second-Stage Bootloader.
TCDM	Tightly-Coupled Data Memory.
Tcl	Tool Command Language, a general purpose scripting language used by Vivado.
UART	Universal Asynchronous Receiver-Transmitter, i.e., a serial port.
UPM	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid.
VCD	Value Change Dump, a file format for storing waveforms.

Contents

Abstract	iii
List of Acronyms	vii
List of Figures	xiii
List of Tables	xv
List of Listings	xvii
1 INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background	1
1.2 Motivation	1
1.3 Objectives	3
1.4 Document Structure	4
2 TECHNOLOGY BACKGROUND	5
2.1 An Overview of RISC-V Cores	5
2.1.1 RISC-V and processor terminology	5
2.1.2 Open-source RISC-V implementations	6
2.2 RISC-V ISA Extension Interfaces	7
2.2.1 RoCC	7
2.2.2 CV-X-IF	8
2.3 On-Chip Interconnects in SoCs	8
2.4 Open-Source Platforms with Application-Class RISC-V Host Processors	8
2.4.1 Cheshire	9
2.4.2 Carfield	9
2.4.3 CVA6 Development Platform	10

2.4.4	Snitch cluster	10
2.4.5	Hero	11
2.4.6	Chipyard	12
2.4.7	ESP	12
2.4.8	OpenPiton	13
2.4.9	BlackParrot	14
2.5	Discussion	14
2.5.1	Host processors	14
2.5.2	Interconnects and accelerator interfaces	14
2.5.3	Peripherals	17
2.5.4	Hardware description languages	17
2.5.5	Configuration tools	17
2.5.6	Simulation and synthesis tools	18
2.6	Platform Selection	18
2.7	The STRELA CGRA and its Integration in the X-Heep Platform	19
2.7.1	X-Heep integration	19
2.8	An Introduction to AXI4	23
2.9	Introduction to the Verilator SystemVerilog Simulator	26
3	THE CVA6 DEVELOPMENT PLATFORM IN PRACTICE	27
3.1	Structure of the Source Files	27
3.2	Simulation and Synthesis Scripts	28
3.2.1	Simulation scripts	28
3.3	Synthesis and Implementation	30
3.4	Project Configuration	31
3.5	FPGA Emulation of the CVA6 Development Platform	31
3.5.1	Introduction	31
3.5.2	The KC705 development board	32
3.5.3	CVA6 JTAG debugging through BSCANE2	33
3.5.4	Compiling and running a bare-metal program	34
3.5.5	Adding an Integrated Logic Analyzer (ILA)	35
3.5.6	Using an ILA while running a program with GDB with a shared JTAG port	36
3.6	Integration of Custom Accelerators	37

3.7	Support for Multiple Outstanding Transactions	41
3.8	Modifications to Enable Cache Flushing	43
4	DEVELOPMENT OF A MODULE FOR CGRA INTEGRATION	45
4.1	Introduction and Requirements	45
4.2	CGRA Module Structure	46
4.3	Design of an AXI4 DMA Interface for the STRELA CGRA	47
4.3.1	Architecture of the DMA interface	47
4.3.2	Operation of the DMA interface	49
4.4	Simulation Environment for the CGRA Module	50
4.4.1	Simulation environment structure	50
4.4.2	Simulation environment scripts	51
4.4.3	CGRA module simulation results	52
4.5	CGRA Module Integration and use from a Bare-metal Program	53
5	USE OF THE ACCELERATOR UNDER LINUX	55
5.1	Preparing an Embedded Linux Image with the CVA6-SDK	55
5.2	Compiling and Running a Program under Linux	57
5.3	Kernel Module Development	58
5.3.1	Introduction	58
5.3.2	Kernel module functionality	58
5.3.3	Kernel module compilation	60
5.3.4	Kernel module loading and unloading	60
5.4	Using the Accelerator from Userpace	62
6	EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS	63
6.1	Resource Utilization Metrics	63
6.2	Proposed Applications for Performance Evaluation	65
6.2.1	ReLU	65
6.2.2	2D convolution	66
6.3	Execution Time Metrics	67
6.3.1	ReLU	67
6.3.2	2D convolution	70
6.4	On the Overhead of Linux	72

6.4.1	Time measurement procedure	72
6.4.2	Overhead of the Linux implementation	73
7	CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK	75
7.1	Conclusions	75
7.2	Future Work	76
8	PLANNING, BUDGET AND IMPACT	77
8.1	Socioeconomic and Environmental Impact	77
8.2	Legal and Ethical Concerns	77
8.3	Contribution to UN's Sustainable Development Goals	77
8.4	Planning and Budget	78
8.4.1	Planning	78
8.4.2	Budget	79
	Bibliography	85

List of Figures

2.1	Cheshire block diagram [4].	9
2.2	Simplified Carfield block diagram. Adapted from [5].	10
2.3	Simplified CVA6 Development Platform block diagram. Adapted from [6].	10
2.4	A snitch cluster as implemented in Occamy, with eight core-complexes with FPUs and an additional one for DMA control [7].	11
2.5	OpenPiton architecture. (a) Tile. (b) Chipset. (c) Multi-chip network. Adapted from [8].	13
2.6	CGRA MAC and ReLU data-flow graphs and mapping. Adapted from [3].	20
2.7	X-Heep platform block diagram [9, p. 9].	21
2.8	Contiguous and interleaved addressing example, with two memory banks.	21
2.9	Data provisioning mechanism for the STRELA implementation on the X-Heep platform [3].	22
2.10	AXI4 read channels [10, p. 24].	23
2.11	AXI4 write channels [10, p. 24].	24
2.12	AXI4 valid and ready handshake. Adapted from [10, p. 39].	24
2.13	AXI4 4-beat read transaction. (a) One outstanding transaction. (b) Multiple outstanding transactions. Adapted from [11].	25
3.1	ALU operands and output for the highlighted instruction of Listing 3.1.	30
3.2	FPGA emulation block diagram. Rounded corners indicate software components or hardware components in the reconfigurable FPGA fabric.	31
3.3	Xilinx KC705 FPGA development board.	32
3.4	Custom accelerator connection to the AXI4 crossbar.	37

3.5	An old version of the RISC-V atomics module limits outstanding transactions to one. As shown, its ar_ready signal is only active for one cycle at a time.	41
3.6	ILA trace showing RAM latency and outstanding transactions.	42
4.1	Module for CGRA integration connected to the crossbar of the CVA6 Development Platform.	45
4.2	Module for CGRA integration, including the DMA interface, CSRs, and AXI adapters.	47
4.3	DMA interface block diagram.	48
4.4	Simulation environment block diagram.	51
4.5	Simulation traces.	52
4.6	ReLU configuration with 10 outstanding transactions.	54
4.7	ReLU configuration with 24 outstanding transactions.	54
6.1	Resource utilization for 24 outstanding transactions.	64
6.2	Resource utilization for 10 outstanding transactions.	64
6.3	ReLU CGRA mapping [3].	65
6.4	2D convolution CGRA mapping.	66
6.5	2D convolution implementation using the CGRA.	67
6.6	ReLU. Effect of unrolling on execution time.	68
6.7	ReLU 16 kB, 10 outstanding transactions.	69
6.8	ReLU 32 kB, 10 outstanding transactions.	69
6.9	ReLU 16 kB, 24 outstanding transactions.	70
6.10	ReLU 32 kB, 24 outstanding transactions.	70
6.11	Conv2D 32x32, 10 outstanding transactions.	71
6.12	Conv2D 64x64, 10 outstanding transactions.	71
6.13	Conv2D 32x32, 24 outstanding transactions.	72
6.14	Conv2D 64x64, 24 outstanding transactions.	72
8.1	UN's sustainable development goals [12].	78
8.2	Gantt chart of this work.	78

List of Tables

2.1	Application-class RISC-V open-source SoC overview.	15
2.2	Development environment and tools.	16
2.3	AXI4-Lite interface signals [10, p. 126].	25
6.1	Resource utilization for 24 outstanding transactions, with the XC7K325T-2FFG900C Kintex-7 FPGA.	63
6.2	Resource utilization for 10 outstanding transactions, with the XC7K325T-2FFG900C Kintex-7 FPGA.	64
6.3	Execution time in baremetal and under Linux on a 650 MHz dual-core Arm Cortex-A9.	73
8.1	Budget for this work.	79

Listings

3.1	ELF file RISC-V disassembly.	29
3.2	Sample execution of OpenOCD.	34
3.3	Sample memory access with GDB.	34
3.4	Sample program execution with GDB.	35
3.5	Commands for ILA IP generation.	35
3.6	ILA IP in <code>corev_apu/fpga/scripts/run.tcl</code>	35
3.7	ILA instance in the SystemVerilog code.	36
3.8	Changes in <code>cva6/Makefile</code>	37
3.9	Changes in <code>corev_apu/tb/ariane_soc_pkg.sv</code>	38
3.10	Changes in <code>corev_apu/fpga/src/ariane_xilinx.sv</code>	38
3.11	Procedure to regenerate the Xilinx IPs for the KC705 board.	40
3.12	Configuration of the number of outstanding transactions in <code>corev _apu/fpga/src/ariane_xilinx.sv</code>	42
3.13	Machine-mode cache flushing.	43
4.1	<code>verilator_public</code> comment usage example.	51
4.2	Accessing a signal from a C++ testbench.	51
4.3	Extract of a baremetal program using the CGRA.	53
5.1	Extracts of terminal output during boot.	56
5.2	Changes to <code>cva6-sdk/configs/busybox64.config</code>	57
5.3	Changes to <code>cva6-sdk/configs/linux64_defconfig</code>	57
5.4	Makefile for kernel module compilation.	60
5.5	Kernel module loading and unloading.	61
5.6	The loaded driver visible in Linux.	61
5.7	Extract of the user-space program.	62

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

This master thesis has been developed at the Center for Industrial Electronics (CEI), which belongs to the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM). The work targets the development of edge nodes for the cloud-edge continuum, applying technologies related to the CEI's research lines on *Coarse-Grain Reconfigurable Arrays* (CGRAs) and RISC-V processors. It has been developed in the context of the MYRTUS project [2], funded by the European Union with grant number 101135183.

The material in Section 1.2 and Sections 2.1–2.6 of this document is based on previous work presented by the author [13] as part of the *Initiation to Research* course of the Master in Industrial Electronics.

1.2 Motivation

Internet of Things (IoT) architectures are typically organized as multi-layer structures, including: the *edge*, which contains devices that interact with the real world and acquire data, usually with very limited resources; the *cloud*, which hosts most computing resources; and the *fog*, that serves as an interface between edge and cloud, also offering computation capability close to where data is produced [1].

Traditionally, the large amounts of data generated on edge devices have been processed in the cloud in a centralized manner. This approach suffers from latency and scalability problems, and increasing concerns about data privacy, issues that can be addressed by moving part of the computing effort to the edge devices themselves [1].

Deployment and maintenance of distributed applications on the edge have specific challenges, particularly when treating devices as independent entities. To tackle these challenges, the concept of the cloud-edge continuum envisions edge, fog, and cloud as belonging to a single space where tasks are dynamically scheduled, as dictated by demand.

A set of requirements can be defined for edge nodes intended to operate in this context. For example, the need for interoperability and to support widely adopted technologies warrants running an operating system –typically Linux– on the nodes. This drives the requirement of an application-grade processor.

Furthermore, nodes must be able to adapt to the different workloads presented to them, while having enough computing power to meet latency requirements. Reconfigurable accelerators are, therefore, well suited for working together with the processor towards increasing node flexibility and performance.

The MYRTUS Horizon Europe project [2] targets the cloud-edge continuum infrastructure and the orchestration of workloads between devices. This task distribution can be horizontal, among edge devices, and vertical (e.g., edge to fog), as well as within individual devices or computing nodes (e.g., software/hardware partitioning).

The MYRTUS project lays out two use cases for testing the developed infrastructure and techniques [14], [2, p. 4]:

- Healthcare, specifically telerehabilitation, where patients interact with edge nodes while performing their therapy at home, being remotely supervised by a therapist.
- Mobility, specifically traffic intersection safety, where tasks include predicting conflicts such as rule violations and collisions. Tasks will be offloaded from on-site edge nodes to fog or cloud as a function of their complexity and allowed latency.

UPM-CEI participates in the MYRTUS project intending to develop edge nodes that act as components of the computing continuum. These nodes are to integrate open-source RISC-V processors and CGRAs as accelerators, to fulfill the cited needs of local processing and adaptability [2].

RISC-V is an open, royalty-free, *Instruction Set Architecture* (ISA) standard that is being widely adopted both in academia and industry. It is also endorsed by European authorities, aiming to maintain sovereignty and competitiveness in this space, reducing dependence on proprietary solutions [15]. The use of a royalty-free ISA and the availability of open-source implementations are also advantageous for future ASIC (Application-Specific Integrated Circuit) developments.

In turn, CGRAs are reconfigurable devices made up of *Processing Elements* (PEs) that are configured, at a functional unit level, to accelerate a portion of a target application [16]. This run-time configurability allows the acceleration of various workloads, as determined by the tasks to be performed and their distribution among the nodes.

A RISC-V processor and a CGRA cannot operate as standalone components, requiring peripherals, such as memory and memory controllers, external interfaces, debug hardware, and a suitable on-chip interconnect. Most of these components can be integrated on a single Integrated Circuit (IC) instead of being mounted as individual

devices on a printed circuit board. The resulting device becomes a *System on Chip* (SoC), which has cost, speed, and reliability advantages over the multiple device approach [17, 2].

An alternative to SoCs is the *System on Package* (SoP) concept, where several dies or *chipselets* are integrated into a single package. This has other advantages, such as the possibility of using different manufacturing processes for each chiplet, the opportunity for design reuse, and a higher yield. Yet, SoPs fall outside the scope of this work, whose main focus is on SoCs.

1.3 Objectives

This work aims to integrate the STRELA [3] CGRA, developed at CEI, as an accelerator attached to an application-class RISC-V processor, conforming an SoC, and evaluate its performance when accelerating a set of tasks. The resulting system will then serve as a starting point for developing an edge node for the cloud-edge continuum.

To achieve this, the following detailed objectives are defined:

- Provide an overview of open-source platforms from the state of the art with application-class RISC-V host processors.
- Select one of these platforms as the starting point for this work.
- For the selected platform, replicate existing simulation and FPGA synthesis flows and make the modifications needed to use development boards available at CEI. Develop and document useful procedures when working with this platform that act as a guide for future developments.
- Introduce the STRELA CGRA and technologies relevant for its integration as an accelerator in the selected platform.
- Develop the necessary hardware for the integration of the STRELA CGRA in the selected platform, with Direct Memory Access (DMA) capabilities for input and output data, and configuration and control through a memory-mapped interface.
- Evaluate the performance of the accelerator in a bare-metal environment.
- Enable the use of the accelerator from a Linux user process and evaluate its performance under this use case.

1.4 Document Structure

This document is organized into chapters, the first of which is this introduction. The rest of the chapters include the content described below:

Chapter 2 introduces RISC-V architectures and gives an overview of open-source SoC platforms using application-grade RISC-V processors. Among these, the CVA6 Development Platform is selected for use in this work. Then, the STRELA CGRA accelerator is presented, followed by an introduction to AXI4 –an interface specification for SoC interconnect–, and to the Verilator SystemVerilog simulator.

Chapter 3 details how the sources for the CVA6 Development Platform are organized, how the simulation and synthesis flows work, and the specifics of working with this platform with the KC705 FPGA development board. It also delves into how accelerators may be integrated into the platform’s interconnect.

Chapter 4 goes over the design and simulation of a CGRA module that enables the integration of the STRELA CGRA into the CVA6 Development Platform. This module includes a custom DMA interface that provides the accelerator with configuration and data from main memory.

Chapter 5 describes the procedures to prepare an embedded Linux image that can boot on the CVA6 Development Platform, the cross-compilation and execution of user programs under Linux, and the development of a Linux kernel module that acts as a device driver, allowing the use of the CGRA accelerator from within a user program.

Chapter 6 presents resource utilization and execution time metrics for the design. A selected set of tasks is executed both on the CPU and with the aid of the accelerator, in bare-metal and under Linux. Results are graphed and discussed.

Chapter 7 provides some conclusions and proposes future work.

Chapter 8 includes planning and a budget for this work and discusses aspects related to its socioeconomic and environmental impact.

Chapter 2

TECHNOLOGY BACKGROUND

This chapter introduces RISC-V and gives an overview of the most relevant open-source SoC platforms using application-grade RISC-V host processors available in the open-source community. One of these platforms is then selected for use in this work. Then, the STRELA CGRA is presented, followed by an introduction to AXI4 –an interface specification for SoC interconnect–, and to the Verilator SystemVerilog simulator.

2.1 An Overview of RISC-V Cores

This section presents some of the open-source RISC-V cores used by the selected set of SoC platforms presented later in Section 2.4, either as application-grade host processors or as part of accelerators.

2.1.1 RISC-V and processor terminology

A given RISC-V core implements a subset of the RISC-V ISA, which adheres to the following naming convention [18, p. 573]: A base n -bit ISA, either integer (RVnI) or reduced integer¹ (RVnE) is followed by letters denoting a set of standard extensions. Examples are: M for multiply/divide; F, D for single and double precision floating point; and C for compressed instructions. Finally, G –general– includes the IMAFDZicsr_Zifencei extensions, adding atomic operations, Control-Status Registers (CSRs), and fence instructions to the base extensions.

RISC-V CSRs are accessed via special instructions and allow the control and monitoring of certain aspects of CPU operation. Examples include cache configuration, handling exceptions, and performance counters. In a more general sense, peripherals usually have memory-mapped CSRs.

Users may also add their custom extensions to a CPU implementation, either by modifying the RTL description or through an ISA extension interface, if available.

The RISC-V ISA leaves free encoding space for such *custom instructions*, so their use is compatible with the standard ones [18, p. 566]. Custom instructions can, for example, be used to control an accelerator as an alternative to memory-mapped registers.

Different amounts of instruction level parallelism can be implemented on a processor using techniques such as *pipelining* –with a different number of stages–, *multiple-issue*, and *out-of-order execution* [19, p. 358-367]. Multiple-issue processors have additional hardware that allows more than one instruction to be launched per clock cycle. Out-of-order execution takes into account data and control dependencies and executes instructions independently of the order in which they were fetched. Instructions can also be executed speculatively by assuming, e.g., the outcome of a branch.

An instruction is said to be *committed* when it takes effect over programmer-visible registers or memory. This is usually done in-order, committing speculatively executed instructions only if the assumptions made when issued were correct.

2.1.2 Open-source RISC-V implementations

One of the most prolific projects in the field of open-source SoCs and RISC-V is PULP (ETH Zurich, University of Bologna). Several cores have originated in the framework of the PULP project, with some being later contributed to non-for-profit organizations focused on open-source IP, such as the OpenHW Group [20] and lowRISC [21]. These organizations have taken over the maintenance and further development of these cores. Examples include:

- Ariane, an RV64GC application-class core focusing on speed and operating system support. It is a single-issue, out-of-order execute, in-order commit core with a 6-stage pipeline. It was contributed to the OpenHW group in 2020 [22, 48], where it is now the CVA6 core [23], with added support for a 32-bit configuration [24].
- RI5CY, an RV32IMFC single-issue, in-order core with a 4-stage pipeline and custom DSP extensions. It was contributed in 2020 to the OpenHW Group, where it is now maintained under the name CV32E40P [25].
- Zero-riscy, an RV32IMC/RV32EMC, single-issue, in-order, 2-stage core, targeting low-power and low-area [26]. It was contributed to lowRISC, where it is now the Ibex RISC-V core [27].
- Snitch, an RV32I/RV32E, single-issue, in-order, single-stage core designed for energy efficiency and minimum area [28].

Two application-class RISC-V cores have been developed at U.C. Berkeley as part of the Rocket Chip SoC generator [29]:

¹The reduced integer base ISA has 16 registers instead of the usual 32.

- Rocket: A 5-stage single-issue, in-order, RV32G/RV64G application-class core.
- BOOM: A 7-stage multiple-issue, out-of-order RV64G application-class core.

The BlackParrot project, by the University of Washington and Boston University, has developed:

- BlackParrot: An 8-stage, in-order, single issue, RV64GC application-class core [30].

Finally, Gaisler offers the NOEL-V family of RISC-V processors [31] geared towards space applications, with limited GPL open-source licenses or commercial licenses that include fault-tolerance features [32, p. 10]. Available configurations range from high-performance RV64GC dual-issue, in-order cores to lower-end RV32IMA microcontroller-class cores [32, p. 1834].

2.2 RISC-V ISA Extension Interfaces

As noted in Section 2.1, the RISC-V ISA may be extended with custom instructions through ISA extension interfaces. This section introduces the interfaces used by the cores in Section 2.1: CV-X-IF (Core-V eXtension Interface) [33], used in CVA6 and CV32E40P; and RoCC (Rocket Chip Custom Coprocessor Interface) [29], [34, p. 25] for the Rocket and BOOM cores.

2.2.1 RoCC

The RoCC interface comprises several sub-interfaces with valid/ready handshaking signals. The processor will detect custom instructions and forward them to an accelerator via a *command interface*, which includes the instruction word and source register values. The accelerator, in turn, can reply through a *response interface*, with the contents of a destination register.

Several bits on the instruction word signal whether source or destination registers will be employed. This influences possible pipeline stalls, e.g., while the processor waits for the accelerator to deliver a result. A further *function* instruction field defines the operation to be performed by the accelerator.

The accelerator can access the processor's data cache through *memory request* and *memory response* interfaces.

An extended version of RoCC allows access to the core's floating-point unit and page table walker, as well as accessing memory via the chip's interconnect.

2.2.2 CV-X-IF

The CV-X-IF works similarly to RoCC, with instructions unrecognized by the CPU being offloaded to the accelerator. The most notable difference is that CV-X-IF is designed to work in a multi-threaded or multi-core environment, with the ability to issue more than one instruction per cycle and deliver the results out of order.

To this end, all transactions with an accelerator are identified with an id unique per in-flight instruction and an optional *hart id*, where a *hart* is a RISC-V hardware thread. A given RISC-V core may support one or more such harts [18, p. 11].

Instructions are issued by means of an *issue interface* and committed or killed through a *commit interface*, with the accelerator able to execute speculatively. Register operands are obtained via a *register interface*, and results are written back into the register file through a *result interface*.

At the time of writing, interfaces to the processor's caches are not defined within the specification, as opposed to RoCC. Nonetheless, an accelerator can access memory through the chip's interconnect.

2.3 On-Chip Interconnects in SoCs

A critical part of SoC design is the on-chip interconnections required for communicating processors, accelerators, peripherals, and memory. The main options are *shared buses*, *crossbars*, and *Networks on Chip* (NoCs) [35, p. 2]. Buses excel in latency and resource utilization yet have low bandwidth. Crossbars allow several low-latency simultaneous transactions at the cost of high area and poor scalability. Meanwhile, NoCs, with a structure similar to Internet networks, excel in scalability and bandwidth [35, p. 2], being best suited to, e.g., high core count SoCs. A NoC can have several layers or *planes* for separating different types of traffic or for increased bandwidth.

2.4 Open-Source Platforms with Application-Class RISC-V Host Processors

This section introduces the platforms evaluated as part of this work. Each platform is briefly described, and their characteristics are summarized in Table 2.1, with details of the development environment on which they rely in Table 2.2. The latter includes the *Hardware Description Language* (HDL) that the platforms are written in, such as SystemVerilog or VHDL.

2.4.1 Cheshire

Cheshire [36] is a minimal host platform built around a CVA6 core. This core interfaces with the rest of the system via an AXI4 crossbar (Figure 2.1). Besides a last-level cache and a DRAM memory controller, the SoC includes peripherals such as UART, SPI, I2C, VGA, and GPIOs. An interrupt controller is also present. Provision is made to add domain-specific accelerators to the SoC by connecting them to the AXI crossbar, and a DMA engine is put in place to aid in data transfer to and from accelerators [36].

Initially supporting one core only, Cheshire now supports a configurable number of CVA6 cache-coherent cores, up to a maximum of 31 units. Further configuration parameters are available regarding the presence of specific peripherals and their configuration [4].

Figure 2.1: Cheshire block diagram [4].

2.4.2 Carfield

Carfield [37] is an SoC platform focused on automotive and mixed-criticality applications. It is partitioned into several domains intended for different applications, all interconnected by an AXI-4 crossbar (Figure 2.2). The host domain is built around a dual-core Cheshire system targeting the execution of low-criticality Linux-based applications. A safe domain, intended for safety-critical and real-time tasks, includes three CV32E40P cores in lockstep and ECC (Error Correction Code) memory. A secure domain ensures the system's boot is secure and contains two Ibex cores in lockstep and cryptography accelerators. Finally, an accelerator domain contains a floating-point vector co-processor for computationally intensive control tasks and an integer *Programmable Many-Core Accelerator* (PMCA) for AI workloads [5]. The PMCA is based on the PULP cluster [38], adding to it dual or triple modular redundancy configurations, trading off performance for reliability [37]. Various peripherals have been added to those included in Cheshire, including Ethernet and CAN.

Figure 2.2: Simplified Carfield block diagram. Adapted from [5].

2.4.3 CVA6 Development Platform

The development and verification of the CVA6 core take place within a minimal platform maintained by OpenHW Group [23]. This platform holds the CVA6 core, its L1 caches, boot ROM, RAM controller, a debug module, and a reduced set of peripherals such as an interrupt controller, UART, and SPI. All components in this platform have AXI interfaces and are interconnected via an AXI crossbar, as shown in Figure 2.3 [6].

Figure 2.3: Simplified CVA6 Development Platform block diagram. Adapted from [6].

2.4.4 Snitch cluster

The snitch-cluster [28] is a many-core system geared towards floating-point intensive applications.

The basic unit of organization, termed a *core-complex* (CC in Figure 2.4), couples a minimal RV32I Snitch core with a ten-times bigger floating-point unit (FPU) and an L0 instruction cache. Two custom ISA extensions allow for the more effective use of this FPU.

The next level in the hierarchy is a *hive*, which includes several core complexes that share resources such as an integer multiply/divide unit and an L1 instruction cache.

One or more hives are grouped with scratchpad memory and a DMA engine in a *cluster*. Clusters interface with the rest of the system through several AXI crossbars [28]. A single-hive cluster is shown in Figure 2.4.

A snitch-cluster chiplet implementation, Occamy, includes 24 clusters, each with nine cores, and a CVA6 host core. The system consists of two chiplets and two DRAM memories [39].

Figure 2.4: A snitch cluster as implemented in Occamy, with eight core-complexes with FPUs and an additional one for DMA control [7].

2.4.5 Hero

Hero (Heterogeneous Research Platform) [40] integrates a host with one or more application-class cores (64-bit CVA6 or ARMv8) with a PMCA based on 32-bit RISC-V cores (either the PULP cluster with the CV32E40P core or the Snitch cluster with the snitch core). Each host core has a private L1 cache, and all share an L2 cache. The accelerator clusters share a software-managed L2 *Scratch-Pad Memory* (SPM), with each having a private L1 SPM, also software-managed [40].

The access from the accelerator cores to the L1 SPMs is done through a Tightly-Coupled Data Memory (TCDM) interconnect that leverages memory banks interleaved at the word level to emulate a multi-ported memory [41, p. 9].

The first Hero implementation, on a Xilinx Zynq Ultrascale MPSoC, uses a built-in ARMv8 Cortex-A53 as a host processor, while the PMCA is implemented in the FPGA fabric. A second implementation, in progress at the time of writing, implements both a CVA6 host processor and the accelerator in the FPGA fabric [42].

2.4.6 Chipyard

Chipyard [43] is a framework for the development of SoCs, based on the Rocket Chip SoC generator [29], which was developed at U.C. Berkeley. The Rocket Chip generator is implemented using the Chisel HDL, which allows for higher-level hardware descriptions that are later used to produce synthesizable Verilog, as well as C++ simulations. It must be noted that the use of Chisel is not widespread, making configuration and accelerator integration more complex. A GitHub search yields $1.4 \cdot 10^3$ projects using Chisel against $64.6 \cdot 10^3$ for Verilog/SystemVerilog at the time of writing. In addition, Chisel is based on Scala, which has a steep learning curve.

Two RISC-V cores, the Rocket in-order core and the BOOM out-of-order core, can be implemented with a high degree of configurability.

The system is organized in tiles, where a tile may hold a processor, its L1 caches, and, optionally, a tightly coupled accelerator. Accelerators within processor tiles may be integrated as instruction set extensions, implemented within the core's pipeline or through the Rocket Custom Coprocessor Interface. A loosely coupled accelerator may also be instantiated on a dedicated tile [29]. Tiles interface via TileLink, a chip-scale interconnect standard that allows multiple masters to access memory and other slaves, with support for cache coherency. Adapters are provided to interface TileLink with AXI4, AHB, and APB interfaces.

The Chipyard framework builds on the Rocket Chip generator and adds to it further cores (CVA6, Ibex), accelerators (vector, matrix multiplication, cryptography), and peripherals, while allowing non-Chisel IPs to be integrated using Chisel wrappers [43].

2.4.7 ESP

ESP [44] is an SoC design platform whose architecture is structured as a heterogeneous tile grid, interconnected via a multi-plane NoC. Several kinds of tiles are available: processor tiles, memory tiles, accelerator tiles, and auxiliary tiles. The SoC can be configured with the aid of a custom *Graphical User Interface* (GUI) tool [45].

Processor tiles can use the CVA6 64-bit RISC-V or 32-bit Leon3 SPARC application grade cores, or the 32-bit RISC-V Ibex core, with only one processor type per SoC. Each tile has private L1 and L2 caches, supporting cache coherency through three of the six NoC planes. Two further planes are used for DMA transfers, and a last plane is used for Memory-Mapped I/O and interrupts. Memory tiles include Last Level Caches and DRAM controllers [44].

Each tile has a socket for NoC interfacing. This socket provides extra functionalities for accelerators designed with ESP tools, such as DMA and virtual memory. On the other hand, third-party accelerators with standard interfaces, such as AXI, can interface with the NoC through an adapter [44].

2.4.8 OpenPiton

OpenPiton [8] is a framework for building scalable many-core processors, targeting research in hardware architectures and the accompanying software, such as compilers.

It is organized in tiles, interconnected by a NoC with support for cache coherency. As shown in Figure 2.5(a), a tile holds a processor with its L1 cache, a private L1.5 cache, a distributed L2 cache, and NoC routers. All interfacing with the NoC goes through the L1.5 and L2 caches, which are directly connected to the NoC routers. The project first used OpenSPARC T1 cores, tailoring the L1.5 cache interface (CCX) to that core. More recently, OpenPiton has been adapted to support the CVA6 processor [46]. To do so, CVA6’s default L1 instruction and data caches have been replaced by a different L1 cache subsystem tailored to interface with the existing L1.5 cache [47]. The integration effort also includes the addition of peripherals needed by CVA6, such as a RISC-V debug module and interrupt controllers [48].

Accelerators may be integrated into their own tiles and interfaced with the NoC. Interfaces such as AXI may be accommodated through an adapter.

Aside from processor tiles, each chip includes a chipset (Figure 2.5(b)) that holds I/O and a DRAM controller, as well as a “chip-bridge” interface, which allows the extension of the NoC off-chip, as in Figure 2.5(c).

Figure 2.5: OpenPiton architecture. (a) Tile. (b) Chipset. (c) Multi-chip network. Adapted from [8].

2.4.9 BlackParrot

BlackParrot [30] is another tile-based SoC, with tiles interconnected by a NoC with one plane for cache coherency, one for DRAM and FLASH access, and a third plane for I/O and other interfaces.

Core tiles hold a BlackParrot processor with private L1 caches, a slice of the distributed L2 cache, and NoC routers. Additional cache-only tiles can be added to increase the size of the L2 cache.

Accelerators can be integrated on their respective tiles by connection to the NoC, with different levels of cache coherency, from fully coherent to non-coherent designs. In addition to the custom BlackParrot NoC interfaces, adapters for other interfaces, such as AXI, can be used [49, p. 56].

2.5 Discussion

This section compares the main parameters selected as relevant for the SoC platforms reviewed in the previous section, as a step toward platform selection. As noted before, Tables 2.1 and 2.2 summarize this information.

2.5.1 Host processors

Among the available options, the requirement to use the Chisel language is a barrier to adopting the Rocket and BOOM cores, and the BlackParrot core does not have an ISA extension interface. There are also no safety-critical requirements that would call for using a NOEL-V core. Thus, among the evaluated options, the preferred choice for a host processor is CVA6. In addition, the CVA6 core is under the umbrella of the OpenHW Group, which may imply it is better maintained.

Regarding the number of host processors, a single core would be enough for a simple edge node. There are no performance requisites that would warrant the additional complexity brought on by many-core platforms such as OpenPiton.

2.5.2 Interconnects and accelerator interfaces

Most considered platforms use crossbar or bus-based interconnects with AXI-4 or custom interfaces, such as Chipyard's TileLink. The remaining ones, focusing on many-core designs, use Networks on Chip as interconnects. Most of them allow the integration of accelerators with an AXI-4 interface via an AXI crossbar or using a NoC adapter. Some others allow accelerators to use virtual memory, such as through the RoCC interface in the case of Chipyard or the accelerator sockets on ESP's tiles.

Table 2.1: Application-class RISC-V open-source SoC overview.

SoC Platform	Host Core	N. cores	Interconnect	Accelerators	Accelerator Interface	Peripherals
Cheshire [36]	CVA6	n	AXI-4 crossbar	DMA + User provided	AXI master ports	UART, SPI, I2C, GPIO, VGA, D2D Link
Carfield [37]	CVA6	2	AXI-4 crossbar	PMCA + Safe, Secure w/ Lockstep	AXI master ports	UART, SPI, I2C, GPIO, USB, CAN, Ethernet WDT, PWM
CVA6 Dev. Platform [23]	CVA6	1	AXI-4 crossbar	User provided	AXI master ports	UART, SPI, SD-card, Ethernet
Switch cluster [28]	CVA6	1	AXI-4 crossbar	PMCA	AXI master ports	UART, SPI, I2C, GPIO, D2D
Hero [40]	CVA6 / ARMv8	n	AXI-4 crossbar	PMCA	AXI master ports	Not mentioned
Chipyard [43]	Rocket, BOOM, CVA6	n	TileLink	Vector, Matrix mult., Crypt. + User provided	TileLink master, ISA ext., RoCC	UART, SPI, I2C, GPIO, PWM
ESP [44]	CVA6, Leon3 (SPARC)	n	6-plane NoC	Tool generated + user provided	Custom, AXI-4 master	UART, SVGA, Ethernet
OpenPiton [46]	CVA6, OpenSPARC T1 (SPARC)	n	3-plane NoC	User provided	Custom	UART, SD Card, Ethernet
BlackParrot [30]	BlackParrot	n	3-plane NoC	User provided	Custom	UART, Ethernet, PCI-E

n cores: Configurable number of cores. PMCA: Programmable Many-Core Accelerator. NoC: Network on Chip. HLS: High Level Synthesis.

Table 2.2: Development environment and tools.

SoC Platform	HDL	Configuration tools	Simulation environment	Supported boards
Cheshire [36]	SV	SV parameters	Questasim	Genesys2, VCU128
Carfield [37]	SV	SV parameters	Questasim	VCU128
CVA6 Dev. Platform [23]	SV	Custom Python script	Verilator, VCS + Spike	Genesys2, KC705*, VC707*, NexysVideo*
Snitch cluster [28]	SV	hjson configuration files	Verilator, Questasim, VCS	No FPGA
Hero [40]	SV	SV parameters	Questasim	ZCU102
Chippyard [43]	Chisel	Chisel parameters	Verilator, VCS, FireSim	VCU118, ArtyA7-35T / -100T
ESP [44]	SV, VHDL + HLS	Custom GUI tools	ModelSim, Incisive, Xcelium	VCU118, VCU128, VC707, XC7V2000T, XC7VU440
OpenPiton [46]	SV	Python hypertext processor	Verilator, VCS, Incisive, ModelSim, Icarus Verilog	Genesys2, VC707, NexysVideo
BlackParrot [30]	SV	SV parameters	Verilator, VCS, DC, Vivado, BSG SV2V, SureLog	Arty A7-100T, Ultra96v2, PynqZ2

* Not actively maintained. SV: SystemVerilog. HLS: High Level Synthesis.

For the intended application, there is no need for the scalability and bandwidth offered by an NoC. A simpler interconnect, less demanding in terms of logic resources, such as bus or crossbar-based, is preferred. There is no specific requirement for virtual memory, though it would be advantageous when using an accelerator under an operating system.

2.5.3 Peripherals

Most platforms include all the peripherals required to boot a simple system, like UART, SPI, and GPIO, together with the JTAG interface for programming and debugging. Some include Ethernet and specialized peripherals, such as CAN (for automotive applications) in the case of Carfield; and VGA (video), for Cheshire and ESP.

A minimal set of peripherals for use during development would be enough for a first prototype. Any application-specific peripheral could be added at a later date. Using a platform with many peripherals, such as Carfield, would incur unnecessary overhead.

2.5.4 Hardware description languages

Most SoCs are written primarily in SystemVerilog, with some including peripherals written in VHDL. Other languages include Chisel, in the case of Chipyard, and High-Level Synthesis (HLS) flows in C/C++ for accelerators, in the case of ESP. It has been noted that Chisel is not widely adopted; it is easier to develop with industry-standard SystemVerilog. Thus, the latter would be the preferred option. HLS flows for accelerator design are also irrelevant for integrating existing accelerators, which is the aim of this work.

2.5.5 Configuration tools

There are a variety of approaches to configure an SoC. Some, e.g., Cheshire or BlackParrot, use SystemVerilog parameters, while others, such as the CVA6 development platform or OpenPiton, use Python scripts for configuration automation. ESP stands out as an example of using GUI tools for this purpose.

The user experience with one or other method cannot be evaluated without working extensively with these projects. Yet, it can be noted that automated scripts or even GUI tools are best suited to large, regular designs, such as those based on tiles.

2.5.6 Simulation and synthesis tools

For simulation, the most popular tools are Verilator² (SystemVerilog, open-source) and QuestaSim³ (SystemVerilog and VHDL, proprietary), with FPGA emulation done in Xilinx FPGAs in all cases, using Vivado⁴ for synthesis.

For simulation, open-source tools such as Verilator are preferred. Vivado licenses are available at CEI, so synthesis is not a concern.

2.6 Platform Selection

Among the SoCs reviewed, Cheshire and the CVA6 Development Platform are the most attractive options for the first implementation of an edge node for the MYRTUS project.

Both are minimal subsystems with simple interconnects, where memory-mapped accelerators can be integrated by connecting them to an AXI4 crossbar. In addition, both have a CVA6 host processor, whose CV-X-IF ISA extension interface could allow the control of the CGRA accelerator via custom instructions, an option probably required in future node extensions.

Regarding the development environment, both platforms are written in SystemVerilog. By default, the CVA6 development platform has support for simulation with Verilator and can be configured to run on a KC705 FPGA development board, available at CEI. Meanwhile, Cheshire's simulation scripts are written for QuestaSim and do not initially support the cited board.

For these reasons, an initial prototype will be based on the CVA6 Development Platform, with Cheshire being considered at a later date.

²<https://www.veripool.org/verilator/>

³<https://eda.sw.siemens.com/en-US/ic/questa/simulation/advanced-simulator/>

⁴<https://www.xilinx.com/products/design-tools/vivado.html>

2.7 The STRELA CGRA and its Integration in the X-Heep Platform

STRELA [3] is a CGRA targeted at the low-power embedded domain. It includes 16 Processing Elements arranged in a four-by-four grid. These PEs are capable of executing integer arithmetic (addition, subtraction, multiplication) and logical operations (shift, and, or, xor), as well as comparisons and branching. The latter are used for conditionals and loop implementation. The CGRA used in this work operates on 32-bit words.

The CGRA's PEs are each configured using a 160-bit (5 x 32-bit) *configuration word*. A configuration word contains a PE identifier and parameters such as the PE's ALU function and multiplexer selections. Only the PEs used in a given application need to be configured.

CGRA configuration is generated by first extracting a *Data-Flow Graph* (DFG) of a given code fragment to be accelerated and then performing the scheduling of operations and their mapping to the CGRA's PEs. Finally, a set of configuration words is generated for this mapping. These tasks can be performed manually or by using architecture-specific compilers.

Figure 2.6 shows two examples of DFGs for multiply-accumulate (MAC) and ReLU⁵ applications, alongside their respective mappings to the four by four CGRA [3]. As few resources are used, the operation can be unrolled, in both cases, by a factor of three. This means that three pieces of data may be processed at a time, always subject to data transfer bandwidth.

So far, these configurations are “one-shot kernels,” as opposed to “multi-shot kernels,” which, due to their complexity, require several CGRA reconfigurations, interleaved with CPU processing, to complete a task [3].

The STRELA CGRA implementation uses *elastic logic*, i.e., valid and ready signals to synchronize computing and data exchange between neighboring processing elements, that make them tolerant to latency. This eases compilation efforts and allows for arbitrary delays in data transfer. The valid/ready handshaking is kept for the CGRA's data inputs, along the top border of the 2D array; and data outputs, along the bottom border.

2.7.1 X-Heep integration

The STRELA CGRA has been previously integrated into an open-source, RISC-V microcontroller platform named X-Heep [9]. The focus of this platform is energy efficiency, through strategies such as clock and power gating.

Figure 2.7 shows a block diagram of the X-Heep platform. It includes a RISC-V CPU from the CV32 family provided by the OpenHW Group, memory arranged

⁵See Subsection 6.2.1.

Figure 2.6: CGRA MAC and ReLU data-flow graphs and mapping. Adapted from [3].

in independent banks, several peripherals, and a debug unit. The interconnect is crossbar-based, with Open Bus Interfaces (OBI). It can be configured to allow access by one or multiple masters at a time.

The internal on-chip memory is divided into banks, which can be configured for contiguous or interleaved addressing. Contiguous addressing (Figure 2.8(a)) enables setting unused banks into lower-power data retention modes at the cost of limited bandwidth for simultaneous accesses (i.e., by different masters). Meanwhile, interleaved addressing (Figure 2.8(b)) allows higher bandwidth for simultaneous accesses, even if addressing nearby memory positions. This has the drawback of a higher energy consumption.

Data transfer to and from the CGRA is carried out by input and output memory nodes. These nodes feed input data on the top PEs and collect data on the bottom PEs through FIFO buffers, as seen in Figure 2.9. CGRA configuration is also fetched from memory by an input memory node.

Figure 2.7: X-Heep platform block diagram [9, p. 9].

Figure 2.8: Contiguous and interleaved addressing example, with two memory banks.

Each node acts as a master on the bus, taking advantage of the multiple-master capability of the interconnect and of the memory banks' interleaved addressing.

A control unit, holding memory-mapped configuration registers, orchestrates the CGRA configuration and input and output data transfers.

These configuration registers or CSRs are meant to set up CGRA operation and hold the following:

- Address and size of the CGRA's configuration.
- Addresses, sizes, and strides for each input memory node, where stride is the distance between pieces of data.
- Address and size for each output memory node. The output stride is fixed to 4 bytes.
- Control bits for starting configuration and execution.
- Performance counters that measure configuration cycles, execution cycles, and memory stall cycles.

Figure 2.9: Data provisioning mechanism for the STRELA implementation on the X-Heep platform [3].

2.8 An Introduction to AXI4

AXI, which stands for Advanced eXtensible Interface, is an interface specification part of the Advanced Microcontroller Bus Architecture (AMBA) by ARM [10].

The CVA6 Development Platform, selected in Section 2.6, has an interconnect based on the AXI4 interface. This section introduces this interface, aiming to serve as a reference for subsequent chapters.

AXI4 defines several independent channels: read address, read data, write address, write data, and write response. These are shown in Figures 2.10 and 2.11, grouped by read channels and write channels, respectively.

Read and write transactions are initiated by a master interface and answered by a slave interface. A master initiates a read transaction by sending an address through the read address channel; from this point, the transaction is said to be *in-flight* or *outstanding* until the slave replies with the requested data through the read data channel.

Similarly, a write transaction is initiated by the master sending an address through the write address channel, followed by data on the write data channel. The transaction is outstanding until the slave signals a write completion through the write response channel.

Figure 2.10: AXI4 read channels [10, p. 24].

Each channel works independently and implements a handshaking mechanism through ready and valid signals. Figure 2.12(a) shows the connections between a source and a destination, with signal timing reflected in Figure 2.12(b). The timing diagram shows how the handshaking works: a data transfer occurs between a source and a destination on the rising edge of the clock when both valid and ready are active.

The full AXI4 specification supports what is known as burst transactions, in which a single address is specified for many data transfers or beats. These bursts can use a fixed address for all transfers, increment from a starting address for accessing contiguous memory, or wrap around a set of addresses.

To enable burst transactions, write address and read address channels contain various signals that encode the type of burst and its length. Meanwhile, the read and write data channels notify the last transfer of a burst. All these additional sig-

Figure 2.11: AXI4 write channels [10, p. 24].

Figure 2.12: AXI4 valid and ready handshake. Adapted from [10, p. 39].

nals are transferred, along with addresses or data, as determined by each channel’s valid/ready handshaking.

Some restrictions apply to burst transactions: they are limited to 256 transfers, must not cross a 4 KiB address boundary, and cannot be terminated early.

AXI4 transfers also have an associated ID so that a master can interleave read requests with different IDs, with the guarantee that those with the same ID will be answered in order.

Other signals include protection (privilege level) and quality of service indication. Finally, the write data channel includes a byte-level strobe signal.

A subset of the AXI4 full specification, known as AXI4-Lite, only includes the most important signals, dropping support for bursts and IDs. Signals for the AXI4-Lite specification are gathered in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3: AXI4-Lite interface signals [10, p. 126].

Global	Write address channel	Write data channel	Write response channel	Read address channel	Read data channel
ACLK	AWVALID	WVALID	BVALID	ARVALID	RVALID
ARESETn	AWREADY	WREADY	BREADY	ARREADY	RREADY
	AWADDR	WDATA	BRESP	ARADDR	RDATA
	AWPROT	WSTRB		ARPROT	RRESP

Though it does not support burst transfers, AXI4-Lite can exercise the full bus bandwidth, owing to the possibility of multiple outstanding transactions. Thus, if the additional functionality of AXI4 is not required, AXI4-Lite has the benefit of simplicity, retaining random access without compromising on bandwidth. Figure 2.13 highlights the benefit of multiple outstanding transactions in the case of a read operation. It is worth noting that the number of outstanding transactions can be limited by the interconnect.

Figure 2.13: AXI4 4-beat read transaction. (a) One outstanding transaction. (b) Multiple outstanding transactions. Adapted from [11].

AXI4-Lite is generally interoperable with AXI4, with the only exception that an AXI master requires an AXI4-Lite slave to mirror the transfer ID. An AXI4-Lite master can drive an AXI4 slave directly.

Aside from AXI4 and AXI4-Lite, there is also a point-to-point interface (non-memory-mapped) called AXI4-Stream that is not used in this work.

2.9 Introduction to the Verilator SystemVerilog Simulator

Verilator [50] was introduced earlier in this chapter as an open-source SystemVerilog simulator. As it will be used in later chapters, this section gives a brief introduction to it. Verilator can be installed from its git repository [51], following the instructions from its documentation page [52].

Verilator is not a traditional simulator because it does not itself simulate the code. Instead, it compiles a SystemVerilog source into a multithreaded C++ program. This program can then be compiled, for example, with GCC, and executed to obtain the actual simulation results. This technique yields significantly faster simulations than what would be possible with interpreter-based simulators.

Verilator does not fully support non-synthesizable SystemVerilog features, such as those used for test benches (e.g., delays, events, or wait statements). However, recent improvements have been made in this respect [53].

Instead of traditional SystemVerilog test benches, Verilator uses C++ test benches, where the module to be simulated is instantiated, stimuli are provided, and results are dumped into a file.

This approach has the advantage of enabling C++ features on test benches and, for example, accessing a module's internal state from the testbench. This can be useful for examining and modifying memory contents.

Another difference between Verilator and other HDL simulators is that Verilator is a two-state simulator [54, p. 55], meaning that it only represents '0' and '1' without support for other values typically used to define the value of logic signals in an HDL, such as 'x' (unknown) or 'z' (high impedance). This results yet again in faster simulations, though it imposes some limitations on initialization error detection and the simulation of three-state logic.

Chapter 3

THE CVA6 DEVELOPMENT PLATFORM IN PRACTICE

This chapter details how the CVA6 Development Platform’s sources are organized, the simulation and synthesis flows, and the particularities of adapting this platform for the KC705 FPGA development board. It also delves into how accelerators may be integrated into the platform’s interconnect.

3.1 Structure of the Source Files

Community projects such as the CVA6 Development Platform benefit from version control systems, which record changes to a set of files gathered in a repository.

One such tool is Git, which is free and open-source. Services such as GitHub work with Git and allow the online hosting of repositories.

Contributors to a given project can *clone* such repositories, work on a local copy, and then propose changes that can be *merged* with the online copy. In Git terminology, changes are made through *commits*, with an associated description and unique identifier [55].

The development of the CVA6 core takes place in OpenHW Group’s `cva6` GitHub repository [23]. This work has been carried out taking commit `33a7a82` (February 14th, 2024) of the repository as a starting point.

The repository holds the RTL code for the CVA6 processor and that of a minimal platform used for simulation and FPGA emulation, referred to as the CVA6 Development Platform in this work. In addition, simulation scripts for Verilator and VCS, as well as co-simulation with Spike, are also included.

Verilator and Synopsys’ VCS are RTL simulators, while Spike [56] is a RISC-V ISA simulator used as a golden reference for verification purposes. For example, CVA6’s simulation and verification scripts can run Verilator and Spike simulations to later compare their results.

The following are the main directories in the **cva6** repository by OpenHW Group:

- **core**: SystemVerilog sources for the CVA6 processor, including the Memory Management Unit (MMU) and the cache subsystem.
- **corev_apu**: Sources for the CVA6 Application Processor Unit (APU), that includes the interconnect and peripherals around the CVA6 core.
 - **corev_apu/tb**: Simulation test-harness with emulated peripherals. The top file is **ariane_testharness.sv**.
 - **corev_apu/fpga**: Sources for FPGA emulation. The top file is **ariane_xilinx.sv**.
- **common**: Sources shared by CVA6 and the CVA6 APU.
- **vendor**: Third-party IP, mostly provided by the PULP project [57], including, e.g., FIFOs, shift registers, and clock dividers.
- **verif**: Verification environment, including simulation and regression tests. The latter ensure that new additions do not alter existing functionality.
- **ci, pd, util**: Scripts related to tool installation and testing.
- **docs**: Documentation.

Additionally, a Makefile on the repository's root holds functionality related to simulation and synthesis.

3.2 Simulation and Synthesis Scripts

The **cva6** repository includes a set of Makefiles and scripts (Python, Shell, and Tcl) that automate the sequence of steps, or *flow*, for simulation and synthesis. This section provides an overview of this functionality.

3.2.1 Simulation scripts

Simulation scripts are located in the following directories:

- **cva6/verif/regress**: Shell scripts to run regression tests and benchmarks. When run for the first time, they also install the required tools, such as Spike and Verilator.
- **cva6/verif/sim/cva6.py**: This Python script allows the configuration of the processor and the simulation of assembly or C programs. The outputs are instruction logs and waveforms in a Value Change Dump (VCD) file¹ that

can be visualized with a waveform viewer. At the time of writing, standard input/output from running programs is not implemented [58].

The `cva6.py` script drives a convoluted simulation flow that involves several make-files on different levels of the repository's hierarchy².

The script receives, among other parameters, the assembly or C sources, compiler flags, and the name of the target simulator. It then uses the RISC-V GCC toolchain to generate an ELF file and calls Verilator, if selected, with the relevant SystemVerilog sources. After Verilator generates an executable model of the CVA6 processor and its test harness, the ELF file is executed on it. The simulation results, namely instruction logs and a VCD waveform file, are saved under `cva6/verif/sim/out_YEAR-MONTH-DAY`.

The exercises proposed in *Advanced Architecture Labs with CVA6* [59] have been helpful for learning how to use the tools and the associated flow. Even though they use an older version of the CVA6 repository, with previous versions of the scripts, they are still useful as an introduction to RISC-V, ELF files, and SystemVerilog, among other required technologies.

An extract of one of the exercises is shown next, which involves simulating an assembly program and observing the waveforms produced in the ALU when an `add` instruction is executed. Listing 3.1 shows the disassembly of the program, with Figure 3.1 showing the ALU operands and the output when the program counter matches that of the `add` instruction. It can be seen that 2022 and 2023 add to 4045. Waveforms are plotted using the GTKwave tool from the VCD waveform file produced by the simulator.

Listing 3.1: ELF file RISC-V disassembly.

```
$ riscv64-unknown-elf-objdump -d asm.elf

asm.elf:      file format elf64-littleriscv

Disassembly of section .text:

0000000080000000 <_start>:
   80000000:  7e600293      li    t0,2022
   80000004:  7e700313      li    t1,2023
   80000008:  006283b3      add   t2,t0,t1
   8000000c:  4501         li    a0,0
   8000000e:  05d00893      li    a7,93
   80000012:  00000073      ecall
```

¹As its name suggests, VCD files store changes in waveforms rather than absolute values. This makes for smaller waveform files.

²The author has raised concerns about this complexity in the project's repository. See: <https://github.com/openhwgroup/cva6/issues/1838>.

Figure 3.1: ALU operands and output for the highlighted instruction of Listing 3.1.

3.3 Synthesis and Implementation

Xilinx Vivado is used for synthesis and implementation, with the following boards directly supported by the CVA6 scripts:

- Digilent Genesys 2 (Kintex-7 FPGA, xc7k325tffg900-2)
- Xilinx KC705 (Kintex-7 FPGA, xc7k325tffg900-2)
- Xilinx VC707 (Virtex-7 FPGA, xc7vx485tffg1761-2)

This support involves the SystemVerilog sources, that, for example, instance a board-specific memory controller. Different constraint files are also available for the different board pinouts. Only the Genesys 2 board support is being actively maintained at the time of writing.

The FPGA synthesis flow is arguably more straightforward than that of simulation: An FPGA target on the Makefile in the repository's root gathers the sources needed for synthesis and calls a further Makefile in `cva6/corev_apu/fpga`, which in turn launches Vivado with several Tcl scripts.

It is worth noting that Xilinx's IPs, such as those for clock generation and memory controllers (located under `fpga/xilinx`), are generated separately and must be regenerated manually if changes are made to their configuration.

After bitstream generation, the last step carried out by the scripts is to generate an MCS file, an Intex Hex file that can be used to program the on-board non-volatile memory with the FPGA configuration. This step erased the Vivado project previously generated by the scripts, which is useful for debugging purposes. To preserve it, this last step was commented out.

3.4 Project Configuration

The project supports several configuration options for the CVA6 processor, for example, 32 or 64-bit, different caches, or MMUs. These configurations are outlined in SystemVerilog packages located in the `cva6/core/include` directory of the project. The appropriate configuration file is selected on the Makefile in the repository's root. The default `cv64a6_imafdc_v_s39_config_pkg.sv` has been used for this work. Specific parameters within these configuration files can be modified through the `cva6.py` script, which can read and alter these files. Example parameters include cache configuration, such as size or associativity.

3.5 FPGA Emulation of the CVA6 Development Platform

This section provides details on working with the FPGA emulation of the CVA6 Development Platform in the KC705 board, including executing and debugging bare-metal programs, as well as observing internal signals with an *Integrated Logic Analyzer* (ILA). The author has contributed documentation in this respect to the CVA6's GitHub repository, available in [60].

3.5.1 Introduction

Figure 3.2 shows a block diagram of the elements involved in the emulation of the CVA6 Development Platform in a Xilinx FPGA, including software tools (Vivado, GDB, etc.) running on a host computer.

Figure 3.2: FPGA emulation block diagram. Rounded corners indicate software components or hardware components in the reconfigurable FPGA fabric.

The FPGA is mounted on a development board, represented in green on the right of Figure 3.2, that includes peripherals, such as DRAM memory; power supplies; and interfacing ICs and connectors.

The reconfigurable region of the FPGA, where the CVA6 Development Platform will be emulated, is known as the FPGA fabric. Besides this region, the device includes fixed hardware that is used for configuration and debugging.

This fixed hardware implements the JTAG standard for on-chip instrumentation, which allows for the configuration of the FPGA fabric and the operation of ILAs for monitoring internal signals in the implemented design. Configuration and ILA monitoring is carried out using Vivado on a host PC, which connects to the FPGA via a USB to JTAG adapter.

The CVA6 processor emulated in the FPGA fabric also uses JTAG for the purposes of programming and debugging. The processor can implement its own JTAG logic and interface through general-purpose pins (Option 1 in Figure 3.2) or use part of the FPGA’s existing implementation, connecting to it through Xilinx’s BSCANE2 IPs (Option 2 in Figure 3.2).

The software tools used for processor programming and debugging are OpenOCD (Open On-Chip Debugger) [61] and the GNU Debugger (GDB), with OpenOCD serving as an interface between the processor and GDB. In addition, terminal input and output are provided by a USB to UART adapter on the board and by a terminal emulator, such as GTKTerm, on the host computer.

3.5.2 The KC705 development board

The development board used in this work is the KC705 development board by Xilinx [62], shown in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Xilinx KC705 FPGA development board.

It hosts a Kintex-7 FPGA (XC7K325T-2FFG900C), 1 GB of DDR3 DRAM memory, and a variety of peripherals (PCIe, Ethernet, GPIO, SD card, UART, LCD, buttons and LEDs, etc.). USB connectors on the left side carry the signals from the UART and JTAG adapters mentioned in the previous subsection to the host computer.

3.5.3 CVA6 JTAG debugging through BSCANE2

The KC705 board has a USB to JTAG adapter based on the FT2232 IC. This IC has two JTAG master ports, but only one of them is used in the KC705 board. This port is intended for FPGA configuration.

Other boards, such as the Genesys 2 [63], have the same JTAG IC, but the second JTAG port is connected to the FPGA's I/O, so that it can be used to debug the design implemented in the FPGA fabric (option 1 in Figure 3.2).

Given the lack of connection of the second JTAG port in the KC705 board, there are two alternatives to be able to debug the CVA6 core in the KC705 board:

- Connect an external JTAG adapter to a board's expansion connector.
- Use the Xilinx BSCANE2 IPs [64], which allow debugging logic implemented in the FPGA fabric through certain registers accessible via the main FPGA's configuration JTAG port (option 2 in Figure 3.2).

The first option requires a JTAG adapter and a suitable connector to interface with the board's FMC interfaces. The specialized connector was not available at the time of writing. Thus, the second option was chosen.

To enable BSCANE2 support, it was necessary to update the debug module used by CVA6 to a newer version. This version allows BSCANE2 as an alternative to the direct connection of the JTAG signals via I/O pins. This was done by updating the `risc-dbg` [65] submodule, by PULP, in the CVA6 repository. For it to synthesize correctly, the `common_cells` submodule, also by PULP, had to be updated as well. Finally, BSCANE2 support is enabled by including the `dmi_bscane_tap.sv` file instead of `dmi_jtag_tap.sv` as sources in the Makefile. These files describe a module with the same external interfaces, yet the former uses the BSCANE2 IPs on its implementation.

The OpenOCD tool, introduced in Subsection 3.5.1, requires a script holding JTAG configuration and details of the IC to be debugged. A suitable script for debugging through BSCANE2 in the Kintex-7 FPGA was adapted from [66] for this project. A sample OpenOCD execution is shown in Listing 3.2, highlighting that the RISC-V processor was found in the configured KC705 board.

GDB can then connect to the server setup by OpenOCD in port 3333 (Listing 3.3) and be used as a first test to examine memory.

Listing 3.2: Sample execution of OpenOCD.

```

$ openocd -f bscan_modified.cfg
xPack Open On-Chip Debugger 0.12.0-01004-g9ea7f3d64-dirty
Licensed under GNU GPL v2
...
Info : clock speed 1000 kHz
Info : JTAG tap: riscv.cpu tap/device found: 0x43651093
      (mfg: 0x049 (Xilinx), part: 0x3651, ver: 0x4)
Info : datacount=2 progbufsize=8
Info : Examined RISC-V core; found 1 harts
Info : hart 0: XLEN=64, misa=0x800000000014112f
Info : starting gdb server for riscv.cpu on 3333
Info : Listening on port 3333 for gdb connections
init routine started
Ready for Remote Connections

```

Listing 3.3: Sample memory access with GDB.

```

$ riscv-none-elf-gdb -ex "target remote :3333" program.elf
...
(gdb) set {int}0x80000000=0x1234
(gdb) x /xw 0x80000000
0x80000000:    0x00001234

```

3.5.4 Compiling and running a bare-metal program

The ability to run and debug bare-metal programs, that is, with complete access to the hardware, without an operating system, is essential for the testing and evaluation of the CGRA accelerator.

An example of bare-metal compilation is provided in the boot ROM for the CVA6 processor. This memory holds the first piece of code executed after the processor is reset. The ROM code, a Makefile, and a linker script are located under `corev_apu/fpga/src/bootrom`. The actual ROM integrated into the CVA6 Development Platform is implemented as a SystemVerilog module generated via a Python script from the ELF file result of the compilation.

The main changes to the Makefile and linker script necessary for compiling general-purpose programs include updating the compiler toolchain to the current one used by CVA6 (it has been changed since the boot ROM was last compiled), and setting the program base address to `0x80000000`, which is the starting point of the system's RAM, where programs are to be loaded.

The boot ROM code includes functions for UART output that can be reused. New functions for UART input and macros to use the built-in timers have been added as part of this work for use during testing and performance evaluation.

The result of the compilation process is an ELF file. GDB can be used to load this file into the target with the `load` command and to execute it with the `continue`

command (Listing 3.4). Other functions offered by GDB are breakpoints and variable inspection.

The running program can be interacted with through the serial port. This can be done using any terminal emulator, such as GTKterm.

Listing 3.4: Sample program execution with GDB.

```
$ riscv-none-elf-gdb -ex "target remote :3333" program.elf
...
(gdb) load
Loading section .text.init, size 0x88 lma 0x80000000
...
(gdb) continue
Continuing.
```

3.5.5 Adding an Integrated Logic Analyzer (ILA)

Integrated Logic Analyzers are invaluable tools to debug hardware designs while running on an FPGA. A Xilinx ILA IP is found in `cva6/corev_apu/fpga/xilinx/xlnx_ila`, and can be used as follows:

- First, the number of signals and bit widths can be configured in `xlnx_ila/tcl/run.tcl`
- Second, the IP can be generated by running the commands in Listing 3.5.

Listing 3.5: Commands for ILA IP generation.

```
$ cd corev_apu/fpga/xilinx/xlnx_ila/
$ export XILINX_PART=xc7k325tffg900-2
  export XILINX_BOARD=xilinx.com:kc705:part0:1.5
  export BOARD=kc705
  export CLK_PERIOD_NS=20
$ vivado -mode batch -source tcl/run.tcl
```

- Third, the ILA IP must be included in `corev_apu/fpga/scripts/run.tcl` as shown in Listing 3.6.

Listing 3.6: ILA IP in `corev_apu/fpga/scripts/run.tcl`.

```
read_ip { \
  ...
  "xilinx/xlnx_ila/xlnx_ila.srcs/sources_1/ip/xlnx_ila/
  xlnx_ila.xci" \
}
...
launch_runs synth_1
wait_on_run synth_1
open_run synth_1

write_debug_probes -force work-fpga/debug_nets.ltx
```

- Finally, the ILA can be instantiated in the SystemVerilog code (Listing 3.7).

Listing 3.7: ILA instance in the SystemVerilog code.

```
xlnx_ila ila_test (  
    .clk(clk),  
    .probe0(your_signal_0),  
    .probe1(your_signal_1),  
    ...  
);
```

3.5.6 Using an ILA while running a program with GDB with a shared JTAG port

As there is only one JTAG port available, GDB debugging and ILA monitoring cannot happen at the same time, as both OpenOCD and Vivado would require accessing a single JTAG adapter simultaneously. However, the following procedure has been developed to circumvent this issue:

- First, the Vivado hardware manager is opened, the bitstream is loaded, and the hardware manager is closed to release the JTAG port.
- Second, OpenOCD and GDB are launched, and a program is loaded and executed in the CVA6 Development Platform.
- Then OpenOCD is closed, which keeps the program running and frees JTAG for use by Vivado.
- Finally, Vivado's hardware manager is opened again, and the ILA waveforms are inspected.

Specific actions by the program can be commanded through the UART once the ILA is waiting on a trigger condition. Debug information can also be shown via the UART.

3.6 Integration of Custom Accelerators

As outlined in the objectives, the STRELA CGRA will be integrated into the target platform with DMA capabilities and memory-mapped control.

This section outlines the steps to integrate a generic accelerator with those features into the CVA6 Development Platform. Such an accelerator connects to the AXI4 crossbar via a master port (for DMA) and a slave port (for accelerator configuration), as shown in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: Custom accelerator connection to the AXI4 crossbar.

The first step is to include the accelerator sources in the Makefile on the repository's root so Vivado can find them upon synthesis. This can be done by appending the sources to the `srcs` variable in the makefile, as shown in Listing 3.8. The highlighted lines have been added to the file for this purpose.

Listing 3.8: Changes in `cva6/Makefile`.

```

accelerator_srcs := file1.sv file2.sv ...

src := $(src) $(accelerator_srcs)

src := $(addprefix $(root-dir), $(src))

```

Next, parameters are defined in `ariane_soc_pkg.sv`, with information about the memory mapping of the accelerator's AXI4 slave port. By way of example, in Listing 3.9, a region `64'h1000`³ bytes long starting at address `64'h5000_0000` is reserved for the accelerator. The selected mapping must not conflict with existing ones that are used for other peripherals.

³In SystemVerilog, `64'h1000` is a 64-bit literal with hexadecimal value 1000.

Listing 3.9: Changes in `corev_apu/tb/ariane_soc_pkg.sv`.

```

localparam NrSlaves = 3; // Crossbar slave ports (2 -> 3)

typedef enum int unsigned {
    DRAM      = 0,
    ...
    Debug     = 9,
    Accelerator = 10
} axi_slaves_t;

localparam NB_PERIPHERALS = Accelerator + 1; // Crossbar master ports

localparam logic[63:0] GPIOLength      = 64'h1000;
localparam logic[63:0] DRAMLength      = 64'h40000000; // 1GByte of DDR
localparam logic[63:0] AcceleratorLength = 64'h1000;

...

typedef enum logic [63:0] {
    ...
    GPIOBase      = 64'h4000_0000,
    AcceleratorBase = 64'h5000_0000,
    DRAMBase      = 64'h8000_0000
} soc_bus_start_t;

```

Then, Listing 3.10 shows how the crossbar configuration is updated to include the address mappings defined in Listing 3.9, and how the custom accelerator is instantiated.

It is worth noting that, in general, AXI4 ports and interfaces are named in this project from the point of view of the crossbar. Thus, `master` is an array of AXI4 interfaces that connect the *crossbar's master ports* to the *AXI4 slaves' slave ports*. Likewise, `slave` is an array of AXI4 interfaces that connect the *AXI4 masters' master ports* to the *crossbar's slave ports*⁴.

Listing 3.10: Changes in `corev_apu/fpga/src/ariane_xilinx.sv`.

```

localparam NBSlave = 3; // debug, ariane + Accelerator (2 -> 3)
...

// Crossbar configuration
axi_pkg::xbar_rule_64_t [ariane_soc::NB_PERIPHERALS-1:0] addr_map;

assign addr_map = '{
  '{idx: ariane_soc::Debug, start_addr: ariane_soc::DebugBase,
    end_addr: ariane_soc::DebugBase + ariane_soc::DebugLength},
  '{idx: ariane_soc::ROM, start_addr: ariane_soc::ROMBase,
    end_addr: ariane_soc::ROMBase + ariane_soc::ROMLength},

```

⁴It is the opinion of the author that the project would benefit from more meaningful variable naming conventions.

```

...
'{idx: ariane_soc::GPIO, start_addr: ariane_soc::GPIOBase,
  end_addr: ariane_soc::GPIOBase + ariane_soc::GPIOLength},
'{idx: ariane_soc::DRAM, start_addr: ariane_soc::DRAMBase,
  end_addr: ariane_soc::DRAMBase + ariane_soc::DRAMLength},
'{idx: ariane_soc::Accelerator, start_addr: ariane_soc::AcceleratorBase,
  end_addr: ariane_soc::AcceleratorBase + ariane_soc::AcceleratorLength}
};
...
// Custom accelerator instance
custom_accelerator #(
  .AXI_ID_WIDTH_MASTER ( AxiIdWidthMaster ),
  .AXI_ID_WIDTH_SLAVE  ( AxiIdWidthSlaves ),
  .AXI_ADDR_WIDTH      ( AxiAddrWidth      ),
  .AXI_DATA_WIDTH      ( AxiDataWidth      ),
  .AXI_USER_WIDTH      ( AxiUserWidth      )
) i_custom_accelerator (
  .clk_i                ( clk              ),
  .rst_ni               ( ndmreset_n      ),
  .axi_slave_port       ( master[ariane_soc::Accelerator]),
  .axi_master_port      ( slave[2])
);

```

Finally, some Xilinx IPs have to be updated if there is an increase in the AXI4 ID width, as AXI4 slaves need to support it. This width is given by:

$$\lceil \log_2(\text{Num. Masters}) \rceil + \lceil \log_2(\text{Num. Slaves}) \rceil$$

Before adding the custom accelerator, the slave ID was five bits wide, as given by:

$$\lceil \log_2(2) \rceil + \lceil \log_2(10) \rceil = 5$$

After adding the accelerator, the number of masters and slaves both increase by one, resulting in the slave ID becoming six bits wide:

$$\lceil \log_2(2 + 1) \rceil + \lceil \log_2(10 + 1) \rceil = 6$$

The slave ID width values are hard-coded into the project files of Xilinx IPs and currently have to be changed manually⁵. The relevant files are under `cva6/corev_apu/fpga/xilinx/`, and the necessary changes are as follows:

⁵The author has contributed a warning about this issue to the platform's source code. See <https://github.com/openhwgroup/cva6/pull/1954> and <https://github.com/openhwgroup/cva6/issues/1941>.

CONFIG.ID_WIDTH is changed from 5 to 6 in:

- xlnx_axi_clock_converter/tcl/run.tcl
- xlnx_axi_dwidth_converter/tcl/run.tcl
- xlnx_axi_dwidth_converter_dm_master/tcl/run.tcl
- xlnx_axi_dwidth_converter_dm_slave/tcl/run.tcl
- xlnx_protocol_checker/tcl/run.tcl

C0_S_AXI_ID_WIDTH is changed from 5 to 6 in:

- xlnx_mig_7_ddr3/mig_genesys2.prj
- xlnx_mig_7_ddr3/mig_kc705.prj
- xlnx_mig_7_ddr3/mig_vc707.prj

After the mentioned changes, the IPs have to be regenerated by running their respective Tcl scripts, as in Listing 3.11.

Listing 3.11: Procedure to regenerate the Xilinx IPs for the KC705 board.

```
$ export XILINX_PART=xc7k325tffg900-2
$ export XILINX_BOARD=xilinx.com:kc705:part0:1.5
$ export BOARD=kc705
$ export CLK_PERIOD_NS=20
$ cd corev_apu/fpga/xilinx/xlnx_mig_7_ddr3/
$ vivado -mode batch -source tcl/run.tcl
$ cd ../xlnx_axi_clock_converter/
$ vivado -mode batch -source tcl/run.tcl
$ cd ../xlnx_axi_dwidth_converter
$ vivado -mode batch -source tcl/run.tcl
$ cd ../xlnx_axi_dwidth_converter_dm_master/
$ vivado -mode batch -source tcl/run.tcl
$ cd ../xlnx_axi_dwidth_converter_dm_slave/
$ vivado -mode batch -source tcl/run.tcl
```

3.7 Support for Multiple Outstanding Transactions

The importance of the interconnect allowing multiple outstanding transactions when accessing memory was highlighted in Section 2.8. The AXI4 crossbar used by the CVA6 Development Platform can be configured to support multiple in-flight transactions, yet it was found that, in practice, the `axi_riscv_atomics_wrap` module limited outstanding transactions to 1. This was observed in the ILA traces in Figure 3.5, where the handshaking signals of the module are active for a single cycle. The module is placed between the crossbar and the DRAM memory in the platform, and it performs the atomic memory accesses required for the RISC-V extension for atomic instructions.

A newer version of this module solves this issue, so the project was updated to that version.

Figure 3.5: An old version of the RISC-V atomics module limits outstanding transactions to one. As shown, its `ar_ready` signal is only active for one cycle at a time.

The configuration of the number of outstanding transactions in `ariane_xilinx.sv` is shown in Listing 3.12. It affects both the crossbar and the new atomics module.

After the mentioned changes, Figure 3.6 shows an ILA trace of a read operation with six outstanding transactions. It can be seen that six addresses are sent, with no further addresses until the first piece of data is received. Enabling multiple outstanding transactions increases bandwidth given the high memory latency, theoretically reaching one transaction per cycle if the number of outstanding transactions equals the response latency.

Figure 3.6: ILA trace showing RAM latency and outstanding transactions.

Listing 3.12: Configuration of the number of outstanding transactions in `corev_apu/fpga/src/ariane_xilinx.sv`.

```

localparam axi_pkg::xbar_cfg_t AXI_XBAR_CFG = '{
  NoSlvPorts:      ariane_soc::NrSlaves,
  NoMstPorts:      ariane_soc::NB_PERIPHERALS,
  MaxMstTrans:     6,
  MaxSlvTrans:     6,
  FallThrough:     1'b0,
  LatencyMode:     axi_pkg::CUT_ALL_PORTS,
  AxiIdWidthSlvPorts: AxiIdWidthMaster,
  AxiIdUsedSlvPorts: AxiIdWidthMaster,
  UniqueIds:       1'b0,
  AxiAddrWidth:    AxiAddrWidth,
  AxiDataWidth:    AxiDataWidth,
  NoAddrRules:     ariane_soc::NB_PERIPHERALS
};

...

// Updated to v0.8.2
axi_riscv_atomics_wrap #(
  .AXI_ADDR_WIDTH ( AxiAddrWidth      ),
  .AXI_DATA_WIDTH ( AxiDataWidth      ),
  .AXI_ID_WIDTH   ( AxiIdWidthSlaves  ),
  .AXI_USER_WIDTH ( AxiUserWidth      ),
  .AXI_MAX_READ_TXNS( 6 ),
  .AXI_MAX_WRITE_TXNS ( 6 ),
  .RISCV_WORD_WIDTH ( 64 )
) i_axi_riscv_atomics (
  .clk_i ( clk ),
  .rst_ni ( ndmreset_n ),
  .slv ( master[ariane_soc::DRAM] ),
  .mst ( dram )
);

```

3.8 Modifications to Enable Cache Flushing

When using an accelerator with DMA capabilities and no support for cache coherency, it becomes necessary to flush the processor caches before and after the accelerator accesses memory. This is so that no outdated data is read by either the CPU or the accelerator.

The only way to flush the data cache at the time of writing is by disabling and re-enabling it through a machine-level processor CSR, `CSR_DCACHE`. This is a custom solution, not RISC-V compliant [67].

From a bare-metal C program, the cache can be flushed using the following macro, where `0x7C1` is the number of the `CSR_DCACHE` register.

Listing 3.13: Machine-mode cache flushing.

```
#define FLUSH_D_CACHE() ({__asm__ volatile("csrwi 0x7C1, 0x00"); \
    __asm__ volatile("csrwi 0x7C1, 0x01");})
```

Attempting to use machine-level instructions from within user or supervisor modes triggers an illegal instruction exception. Since the original cache control is a custom solution, to enable cache clearing from within the Linux kernel (supervisor mode) this work adds another custom CSR.

In a CSR's 12-bit number, the top two bits encode whether the CSR is read-only or read/write, and the next two encode the privilege level [68]. The `0x1A0` number is free in the current implementation and corresponds to a read/write CSR accessible from a supervisor or higher privilege level. A CSR with that number was added to the CVA6 processor (`CSR_DCACHE_SUPERVISOR`), with the same functionality as `CSR_DCACHE`. After this change, the cache can be flushed within a kernel module, which will be needed to use the accelerator from within Linux. This will be addressed later on in Chapter 5.

Chapter 4

DEVELOPMENT OF A MODULE FOR CGRA INTEGRATION

This chapter describes the development of a module for integrating the STRELA CGRA into the CVA6 Development Platform. This module includes the CGRA, a custom DMA interface, CSRs, and protocol adapters to connect with the AXI4 crossbar in the target platform, resulting in a module with the same ports as the generic accelerator mentioned in Section 3.6.

4.1 Introduction and Requirements

In order to integrate the STRELA CGRA into the CVA6 Development Platform, a module that includes the necessary hardware for data provisioning via DMA and configuration and control of the accelerator must be developed. Figure 4.1 shows how this CGRA module would connect to the crossbar of the CVA6 Development Platform.

Figure 4.1: Module for CGRA integration connected to the crossbar of the CVA6 Development Platform.

The previous X-Heep integration of the STRELA CGRA was described earlier in Section 2.7. This implementation took advantage of the multi-master capability of

X-Heep’s interconnect and the interleaved addressing of its internal memory banks, enabling multiple simultaneous memory accesses. To this effect, each input and output port of the CGRA had an associated memory node that acted as an independent master on the interconnect. FIFO buffers were present between these nodes and the CGRA’s ports.

Conversely, the CVA6 Development Platform does not have banked memory, so a single access to main memory is supported at a time. Therefore, multiple master ports are not advantageous in this case. This difference is what motivates the development of a novel DMA interface that multiplexes a single AXI4 master port between the input and output ports of the CGRA. A further difference between the implementations is that the interconnect of the CVA6 Development Platform is 64-bit wide, while that of X-Heep is 32-bit wide. The CGRA in both implementations works with 32-bit words.

In the context of offloading a code section for acceleration by the CGRA, the DMA interface must be capable of first configuring the CGRA for the task to be performed, and then of providing it with input data from memory, finally storing output data in memory for further processing by the CPU.

To maintain compatibility with the X-Heep implementation, the DMA interface takes the same parameters of starting address and size in memory for the CGRA’s configuration, and for data regions assigned to each input and output port of the CGRA. Input ports also allow a configurable stride. The module to be developed will expose suitable CSRs so that the running program in the CPU can provide these parameters.

Supporting a variable stride means accessing non-contiguous memory if this stride takes values greater than the accessed word size (32 bits). Thus, the stride requirement rules out AXI4 burst transactions, often needed for high throughput. Instead, the AXI4-Lite subset of the AXI interface will be used, specifying the address of every word that is read or written.

As the DMA interface accesses DRAM memory directly, with no caches in between, there is a high latency between a data request and the associated response. The solution to improve throughput is using multiple outstanding transactions, as noted in Section 2.8. Therefore, the DMA interface to be developed shall include this feature.

4.2 CGRA Module Structure

To address the requirements of the previous section, a module for CGRA integration with the structure of Figure 4.2 is proposed. In addition to the CGRA and the DMA interface, the proposed module includes CSRs for control and configuration, a control unit and performance counters, and adapters for the AXI interfaces.

A first adapter translates an AXI slave to a register interface, a simpler interface

suitable for reading and writing CSRs. A second adapter, from AXI-Lite slave to AXI Master, adds the required signals so that the AXI master port of the module is compatible with the crossbar of the CVA6 Development Platform.

Figure 4.2: Module for CGRA integration, including the DMA interface, CSRs, and AXI adapters.

The module exposes master and slave AXI interfaces, clock, and reset, which are the only signals that need to be connected in the target system.

4.3 Design of an AXI4 DMA Interface for the STRELA CGRA

4.3.1 Architecture of the DMA interface

Figure 4.3 shows the proposed architecture of a DMA interface that fulfills the requirements outlined in Section 4.1, and that will become part of the module for CGRA integration. This design drives the AXI4 master port's read and write channels to read input data for the CGRA from memory, write output data back to memory, and load CGRA configuration, for which input data logic is re-used. As the read and write channels work similarly, the read channel (upper half of Figure 4.3, in blue) will be used as an example for describing the proposed design.

The CGRA is depicted in the center of Figure 4.3, with its input FIFOs along the top border. As there is a single master port connected to the crossbar, input data is directed to a given input FIFO by a demultiplexer.

Address counters in blue on the left side of Figure 4.3 are responsible for generating the addresses for input data, taking the parameters of the starting address, stride,

Figure 4.3: DMA interface block diagram.

and size from CSRs. There is an address counter per input port of the CGRA, with one of them being selected at a time by a multiplexer.

A round-robin arbiter is tasked with driving this multiplexer so that a read request can be carried out, by sending the address generated by a given address counter to the crossbar. The arbiter will cyclically select those counters whose matching input FIFOs have free space.

The proposed design includes a special FIFO, the in-flight FIFO, which keeps track of the read requests that have been sent and their destination input data FIFOs. This element is key in supporting multiple outstanding transactions.

CGRA configuration loading re-uses the input data logic, with additional elements shown in green. These include a dedicated configuration address counter and a shift register that holds a configuration word for a single PE, which is then loaded into the CGRA. An extra signal from the input data multiplexer feeds this shift register.

The write channel logic (lower half of Figure 4.3, in orange) has the same elements as that of the read channel and operates analogously.

4.3.2 Operation of the DMA interface

This subsection provides more detail on the operation of the DMA interface.

A read transaction begins when the address from an address counter selected by the input round-robin arbiter is sent to the crossbar. At the same time, what input FIFO is to receive the requested data is recorded into the read in-flight FIFO, together with information on whether the requested address was for an odd or even 32-bit word. The read transaction is now in-flight or outstanding.

Once the requested data comes back from the crossbar, it will be pushed into the appropriate input FIFO, according to the in-flight FIFO's oldest entry. This entry is then removed from the in-flight FIFO. The odd or even information is used to select the upper or lower 32-bit word of the crossbar's 64-bit data bus.

The input round-robin arbiter only considers those address counters that meet the following conditions:

- The address counter has not yet completed the scheduled count, as per the CSR values.
- The matching input FIFO has enough free space to hold all current outstanding transactions for that FIFO plus the additional one that is being requested.

The second condition guarantees that any incoming piece of data can be stored upon arrival. The number of outstanding transactions bound for a given FIFO is kept track of by counters (not shown in Figure 4.3) that increment when a piece of data is requested and decrement when received.

From within the address counters that meet the above criteria, the round-robin arbiter will select one in a cyclic fashion if:

- The AXI master port's address channel is ready or will be ready for a transaction the following cycle. That is, it is not waiting to complete the previous one.
- The in-flight FIFO is not full.

Write transactions work similarly. A transaction is initiated once a write address is sent to the crossbar, and registered into what is now a pending write FIFO until the crossbar asks for the data to be written. The write transaction will be in-flight until a write completion is received through the write response channel (See Section 2.8). As writes to memory should always be successful, this design ignores the write response channel.

The conditions for the output round-robin arbiter match those for the input, replacing the need for free space on input FIFOs with the requirement that output FIFOs must contain more pieces of data than the number of pending transactions related to that FIFO.

As in the case of the input channel, the number of pending transactions for each output FIFO is kept track of by dedicated counters.

With respect to CGRA configuration, configuration read transactions result in data being shifted into a five-word shift register, that, once full, is loaded into the CGRA, configuring one of its processing elements. The main difference between this shift register and the input FIFOs is that the shift register is always ready to receive data. As a result, transactions are requested continuously until the configuration address counter reaches the scheduled limit.

A downside of the presented design is that the 32-bit accesses on the 64-bit interconnect of the CVA6 Development Platform result in redundant memory operations when addressing a contiguous memory range. Future work may involve adding additional hardware to improve performance in this scenario.

4.4 Simulation Environment for the CGRA Module

For the development and testing of the previously described module for CGRA integration, a simplified simulation environment without the CVA6 processor has been devised. As with the full CVA6 Development Platform, Verilator will be used as a simulation tool. Verilator was introduced earlier in Subsection 2.9.

4.4.1 Simulation environment structure

Figure 4.4 shows the components of the simulation environment. The AXI-CGRA module being developed is connected to an AXI crossbar, the same IP used in the CVA6 Development Platform, with the same configuration. A simulated 64-bit RAM is connected to the crossbar through an AXI adapter.

The AXI CGRA module, crossbar, and RAM are instantiated in a `sim_top` SystemVerilog module, which is then instantiated in a Verilator C++ testbench. This testbench is responsible for generating the clock and the reset signals and dumping a waveform file.

Stimuli can be provided inside the `sim_top` module; for example, the crossbar can be driven to read or write to the AXI CGRA module's registers. Alternatively, the internal state of the modules, such as register or memory contents, can be accessed and modified from within the C++ testbench. This can be enabled by adding the `/*verilator public*/` comment next to a given signal. This comment is understood by Verilator, which will make the C++ class member that represents that signal public, and thus accessible from the testbench [54, p. 50].

For example, Listing 4.1 shows this comment applied to the array that holds RAM contents, and Listing 4.2 how this contents can be accessed from the C++ testbench.

Figure 4.4: Simulation environment block diagram.

Listing 4.1: `verilator_public` comment usage example.

```
logic [63:0] ram_memory_contents [RAM_SIZE-1:0] /*verilator public*/;
```

Listing 4.2: Accessing a signal from a C++ testbench.

```
#include "Vsim_top_sim_top.h"
#include "Vsim_top_test_ram_64.h"
...
dut->sim_top->i_test_ram->ram_memory_contents[0x100] = 0x1234;
```

4.4.2 Simulation environment scripts

A custom makefile has been written to manage the simulation of the CGRA module. The makefile is based on the CVA6 makefiles and on the examples in [69]. This makefile gathers the sources for the CGRA module, and IP from PULP for AXI, FIFOs, etc, that are used in the project. It has the following targets:

- **.stamp.verilate**: Calls Verilator, providing it with the source files and configuration. When Verilator is done, the generated C++ files are built, and the executable is generated.
- **waveform.vcd**: Runs the executable and generates a VCD waveform file.
- **waves**: Calls GTKWave for waveform display, with the generated VCD file and a configuration file for waveform format.

- **lint**: Calls Verilator configuring it for error checking.
- **clean**: Deletes all products of the other targets.

Using the makefile, a system designer can write **make waves** and, if the sources have changed, they will be processed by Verilator, the simulation run, and the resulting waveforms displayed. If the sources have not changed since the last run, GTK-Wave will be called directly with the existing waveform file. In addition, Verilator generates its own makefiles for the compilation of the generated C++ files. These makefiles allow the designer to change the C++ testbench without recompiling the C++ files generated by Verilator. This makes it fast to change stimuli and re-run simulations.

4.4.3 CGRA module simulation results

Simulations executed within the framework described in this section allowed the debugging and testing of the developed CGRA module. The module was tested by executing sample CGRA configurations. The first, "bypass", directly connects each CGRA output to the input above. More detail regarding CGRA configurations is given in Chapter 6.

Figure 4.5 shows some simulation traces, in particular the request and grant signals of the round-robin arbiters, input data FIFO counts, and AXI4 read address and read data channels.

Figure 4.5: Simulation traces.

4.5 CGRA Module Integration and use from a Bare-metal Program

The module developed in this chapter was integrated into the CVA6 Development Platform following the procedure outlined in Section 3.6.

The crossbar was configured to assign a region **0x1000** bytes long at address **0x50000000** to the AXI-Slave port of the CGRA module. This region was free in the memory map, and its size is sufficient to address the module's CSRs.

Listing 4.3 shows how the accelerator can be configured and used from a bare-metal program. Suitable macros have been defined to access the CSRs; for example, the macro `CGRA_CONF_ADDR` finally expands to `(*volatile uint32_t*)(0x50000004)`, where **0x50000004** is the address of the `CGRA_CONF_ADDR` CSR, offset four bytes from the beginning of the memory region assigned to the module.

The first step in using the accelerator is to configure the CSRs with the addresses where the CGRA configuration resides in memory, and with the input and output data ranges where the processor has placed the input data and where it expects the output data to be written, respectively.

Then, the CGRA's state and previous configuration are cleared. After a new configuration is loaded into the CGRA, the task is executed. As a result, the data processed by the CGRA will be available in memory in the output data range for use by the processor. Before accessing this data, the processor must flush its caches to guarantee that it does not work with outdated data previously held in the cache.

Listing 4.3: Extract of a baremetal program using the CGRA.

```
// CGRA's configuration address and size
CGRA_CONF_ADDR = cgra_kernel;
CGRA_CONF_SIZE = cgra_kernel_size_words * 4;

// Input and output addresses, strides and sizes
CGRA_IN0_ADDR = input_buffer;
CGRA_IN0_SIZE = CGRA_IN_BITS_STRIDE_COUNT(0x04, BUFF_SIZE);
...
CGRA_OUT0_ADDR = output_buffer;
CGRA_OUT0_SIZE = CGRA_OUT_BITS_STRIDE4_COUNT(BUFF_SIZE);
...
CGRA_CTRL = CGRA_CTRL_BIT_CLEAR_STATE;
CGRA_CTRL = CGRA_CTRL_BIT_CLEAR_CONFIG;

// Start configuration loading and wait until done
CGRA_CTRL = CGRA_CTRL_BIT_LOAD_CONFIG;
while(!(CGRA_CTRL & CGRA_CTRL_BIT_DONE_CONFIG)){};

// Start execution and wait until done
CGRA_CTRL = CGRA_CTRL_BIT_START_EXEC;
while(!(CGRA_CTRL & CGRA_CTRL_BIT_DONE_EXEC)){};
```

Figures 4.6 and 4.7 show ILA traces of CGRA module's AXI master port, as it reads the CGRA configuration for the ReLU task. Traces are shown with the DMA interface using a maximum of 10 and 24 outstanding transactions, respectively. Both figures have the same time scale, with the configuration with 10 outstanding transactions being much slower (239 clock cycles vs. 88).

Figure 4.6: ReLU configuration with 10 outstanding transactions.

Figure 4.7: ReLU configuration with 24 outstanding transactions.

Chapter 5

USE OF THE ACCELERATOR UNDER LINUX

The developments described in this chapter aim to enable the use of the CGRA accelerator from within a Linux user program. The main contribution of this work in this respect is the development of a Linux kernel module that controls the accelerator and manages a shared memory buffer. In addition, information is presented on creating an embedded Linux image that can boot on the CVA6 Development Platform and on the cross-compilation and execution of user programs under Linux. This chapter ends with an example of a user-space program that uses the accelerator.

5.1 Preparing an Embedded Linux Image with the CVA6-SDK

The CVA6-SDK repository [70] holds a set of scripts to build an embedded Linux image that can run in the FPGA emulation of the CVA6 Development Platform.

A Makefile in the repository's root makes it easy to install the required tools by running `make all` and then build a Linux image with `make images`.

One of the installed tools is the RISC-V cross-compilation toolchain, which is placed under `cva6-sdk/buildroot/output/host/bin`. This toolchain will be used later on in this chapter to cross-compile both user programs and a Linux kernel module.

In addition, the scripts also install Buildroot [71], which is used to handle cross-compilation with the RISC-V toolchain, RAM filesystem, and bootloader (U-Boot). The filesystem includes BusyBox [72], an executable that implements simplified versions of standard UNIX utilities (`ls`, `cat`, `chmod`, `vi`, etc.), optimized for use in embedded systems.

After the Linux image is built, a bootable SD card can be prepared as follows.

First, its disk label, such as `/dev/sdb`, can be found with the following command:

```
$ sudo fdisk -l | grep sd
```

Then, a tool such as GParted can be used to erase existing partitions to later populate the SD card by running:

```
$ sudo -E make flash-sdcard SDDEVICE=/dev/sdb
```

The SD card may now be inserted into the KC705 board, which will boot Linux if the CVA6 FPGA bitstream is loaded.

After resetting the system, the CVA6 processor executes from its internal boot ROM, which holds the *Zero-Stage Bootloader* and the platform's *device tree*. This code will look for a *First Stage Bootloader* (FSBL) in the SD card, copy it to RAM, and begin execution. The FSBL will load the *Second-Stage Bootloader*, U-Boot, which in turn loads and boots the kernel image.

Extracts of the terminal output during the boot process are shown in Listing 5.1.

Listing 5.1: Extracts of terminal output during boot.

```
Hello World!
init SPI
status: 0x000000000000000025
status: 0x000000000000000025
SPI initialized!
initializing SD...
SD command cmd0      response : 01
SD command cmd55     response : 01
...
copying boot image ....
...
U-Boot 2021.07-rc4-g920075ecfa (Jun 25 2024 - 19:30:00 +0200)

CPU:   rv64imafdc
DRAM:  1 GiB
MMC:   xps-spi@20000000:mmc@0: 0
Loading Environment from nowhere... OK
In:    uart@10000000
Out:   uart@10000000
Err:   uart@10000000
Net:   No ethernet found.
Hit any key to stop autoboot:  0
...
#
```

The development of a loadable kernel module will be tackled in Section 5.3. To this end, support for the following commands for the management of loadable modules has to be enabled in the BusyBox configuration: `insmod`, `lsmod`, and `rmmod`. This can be done by updating BusyBox's configuration file, as shown in Listing 5.2¹.

¹See: <https://github.com/openhwgroup/cva6-sdk/issues/43>, <https://bugs.debian.org/cgi-bin/bugreport.cgi?bug=650159>

Listing 5.2: Changes to `cva6-sdk/configs/busybox64.config`.

```
#
# Linux Module Utilities
#
CONFIG_MODPROBE_SMALL=y
CONFIG_DEPMOD=y
CONFIG_INSMOD=y
CONFIG_LSMOD=y
CONFIG_FEATURE_LSMOD_PRETTY_2_6_OUTPUT=y
CONFIG_MODINFO=y
CONFIG_MODPROBE=y
CONFIG_FEATURE_MODPROBE_BLACKLIST=y
CONFIG_RMMOD=y
...
CONFIG_DEFAULT_MODULES_DIR="/lib/modules"
```

In addition, support for unloading kernel modules has to be enabled in the kernel configuration by adding the two lines in Listing 5.3 to the kernel configuration file.

Listing 5.3: Changes to `cva6-sdk/configs/linux64_defconfig`.

```
CONFIG_MODULE_UNLOAD=y
CONFIG_MODULE_FORCE_UNLOAD=y
```

After these changes, the kernel is rebuilt. The configuration it was built with can be seen in `cva6-sdk/buildroot/output/build/linux-v5.10.7/.config`.

5.2 Compiling and Running a Program under Linux

As mentioned, a user-space program can be compiled using the RISC-V GCC toolchain in `cva6-sdk/buildroot/output/host/bin`. This can be done as follows:

```
$ riscv64-buildroot-linux-gnu-gcc main.c -o main.elf
```

The resulting ELF file can be sent to the board by using the serial port, using the `sx/rx` utilities, for example, via `tty/USB0`:

- On the host computer, the serial port is first configured:


```
$ stty -F /dev/ttyUSB0 115200 cs8 -parenb -cstopb -ixon
$ sudo chmod -R 777 /dev/ttyUSB0
```
- Then, `rx` is ran on the target:


```
# rx main.elf
```
- And the file is sent from the host with `sx`:


```
$ sx main.elf < /dev/ttyUSB0 > /dev/ttyUSB0
```

- Finally, the file can then be executed on the target as follows:

```
# chmod 777 main.elf
# ./main.elf
```

5.3 Kernel Module Development

5.3.1 Introduction

For user-space programs to use the accelerator described in previous chapters, they must be capable of:

- Accessing configuration registers located at certain addresses in physical memory.
- Sharing a memory buffer where configuration and data can be placed, accessible both by the user process via its virtual addresses and by the accelerator via its physical addresses.

The first requirement can be met by directly accessing physical memory through `/dev/mem` or using the user space I/O framework. Conversely, the second requirement can only be addressed by writing a kernel module.

To this end, a loadable kernel module has been written as part of this work. Unlike built-in modules, loadable modules can be inserted and removed at runtime [73, p. 5], making development easier.

The following references have helped carry out this task:

- The Linux Kernel Module Programming Guide [74], that includes a brief introduction to kernel modules and several up-to-date (Linux v5.x - v6.x) examples.
- Linux Device Drivers, Third Edition [73], a more in-depth treatment, though outdated (Linux v2.6.10).
- ARTICo³ kernel module [75], a kernel module that implements some of the functionality needed in this work.
- A `dma_alloc_coherent()` example in [76].

5.3.2 Kernel module functionality

The developed module has the following functionality upon insertion:

- Allocates and registers a character device with the kernel.
- Creates a device in `/dev`, accessible by the user.

- Allocates a contiguous memory region with `dma_alloc_coherent()`, which returns a kernel virtual address and a physical address to be used by the accelerator.
- Registers and maps an I/O memory region used to access the accelerator's control and configuration registers.

The requested resources are freed upon module unloading or during insertion if an error occurs.

A Linux kernel module presents an interface based on file operations, that are performed to a device file through which the module is accessed. The developed module implements the following file operations (Listing 5.7 later on shows usage examples):

- `open()` and `close()` (release) keep track of the number of users of the module so that it can only be unloaded when it is not in use.
- `mmap()` maps the memory region allocated on insertion to the userspace so that the user program can access it.
- `ioctl()` allows the user process to configure data transfers and begin execution. IOCTL stands for Input Output ConTroL and allows the user program to send IOCTL *commands* to the module, defined for the specific application.

Three IOCTL commands are supported by the developed kernel module:

- **IOCTL_CGRA_CONTROL**: Sets up the addresses and sizes of configuration and data memory ranges. As the user process does not need to know about physical addresses, configuration and data locations are specified as offsets from the start of the shared memory region instead of as absolute values. The kernel module translates those offsets to physical addresses before writing them to the accelerator's control registers.
- **IOCTL_CGRA_CONFIG**: Commands the accelerator to fetch a new configuration from the shared memory region. It blocks until the accelerator finishes the operation.
- **IOCTL_CGRA_EXEC**: Commands the accelerator to begin execution. It blocks until the accelerator finishes the operation.

Section 3.8 noted the need to flush the processor's caches before and after the accelerator accesses memory to ensure that the correct data is processed. This is still the case with the shared memory region reserved by the accelerator, as it remains cached, with no other possibility allowed by the current cache and MMU implementation.

Therefore, when working under Linux, the kernel module is also responsible of data cache flushing, using the supervisor-mode CSR that was implemented in Section 3.8.

5.3.3 Kernel module compilation

A makefile for kernel module cross-compilation has been adapted from an example in [77]. This makefile is shown in Listing 5.4. The `KDIR` variable points to the kernel sources [73, p. 24], and the `CROSS_COMPILE` variable is the compiler toolchain prefix for the buildroot RISC-V toolchain. An additional target has been added to ease sending the resulting `.ko` file to the board.

Listing 5.4: Makefile for kernel module compilation.

```
PWD := $(shell pwd)

ARCH := riscv

XLEN      := 64
BUILDROOT_DIR := /home/juangranja/Documents/CVA6_SDK/cva6-sdk/buildroot
CROSS_COMPILE := $(BUILDROOT_DIR)/output/host/bin/riscv$(XLEN)
              -buildroot-linux-gnu-

obj-m := cgra_dma.o

KDIR := $(BUILDROOT_DIR)/output/build/linux-v5.10.7

export

default: clean
        $(MAKE) -C $(KDIR) M=$(PWD) modules

clean:
        $(MAKE) -C $(KDIR) M=$(PWD) clean

serial:
        sudo stty -F /dev/ttyUSB0 115200 cs8 -parenb -cstopb -ixon &&
        sudo chmod -R 777 /dev/ttyUSB0 && sx $(basename $(obj-m)).ko
        < /dev/ttyUSB0 > /dev/ttyUSB0
```

5.3.4 Kernel module loading and unloading

Prior to the use of the developed kernel module by a Linux user program in the CVA6 Development Platform, the developed module has to be loaded into the running kernel. Listing 5.5 shows how a kernel module is loaded with `insmod` and unloaded with `rmmmod`. Currently loaded modules are displayed via the `lsmod` command.

Listing 5.6 shows where the resource allocation by the kernel module is seen in Linux:

- `/proc/devices`: Shows the `cgra_dma` device registered by the driver.
- `/sys/class/cgra_dma`: Class created by the driver, where a class is a high-level view of a device.

- `/dev/cgra_dma`: Device file accessed by the user process.
- `/proc/iomem`: Shows the requested I/O memory region for access to the CSRs.

Listing 5.5: Kernel module loading and unloading.

```
# mkdir TEST
# cd TEST
# rx cgra_dma.ko
# ls
cgra_dma.ko
# insmod m.ko
[ 438.411702] cgra_dma: loading out-of-tree module taints kernel.
[ 438.443699] [Mod] Starting insertion
[ 438.519624] [Mod] Success
# lsmod
cgra_dma 5459 0 - Live 0xffffffffdf81303000 (0)
# rmmod cgra_dma
[ 449.692648] [Mod] Exit
# lsmod
#
```

Listing 5.6: The loaded driver visible in Linux.

```
# cat /proc/devices
Character devices:
 1 mem
 2 pty
 3 tty
 4 ttyS
 5 /dev/tty
 ...
252 cgra_dma
253 rpmb
254 gpiochip
 ...

# ls /sys/class
bdi          gpio          leds          mmc_host     spi_master
block       hwmon        mdio_bus     mux          tty
cgra_dma   i2c-adapter mem          net          virtio-ports
devlink     input

# ls /dev
cgra_dma ptyd8          ptys6  ptyx4  ttyb8  ttyq6  ttyv4
 ...

# cat /proc/iomem
10000000-10000fff : serial
20000000-20000fff : 20000000.xps-spi xps-spi@20000000
30000000-30007fff : 30000000.lowrisc-eth lowrisc-eth@30000000
40000000-4000ffff : 40000000.gpio gpio@40000000
50000000-50000fff : cgra_dma
80200000-bfffffff : System RAM
```

5.4 Using the Accelerator from Userpace

Listing 5.7 depicts how the CGRA accelerator can be used from a user-space program via the interface presented by the developed kernel module.

First, the device file is opened, and the `mmap()` function is called, returning a pointer to the shared memory buffer reserved by the driver.

CGRA configuration and input data are then written into the shared buffer at known offsets.

DMA interface configuration, i.e., data offsets, strides, and counts, are written into the `cgra_ctrl` structure. As noted before, instead of addresses, configuration and data locations are specified as offsets from the start of the shared memory region. These will be translated to physical addresses by the kernel module.

Finally, a set of `ioctl()` calls trigger the configuration of the DMA interface with the `cgra_ctrl` parameters, the CGRA configuration loading, and the task execution.

The last step involves retrieving output data from the shared memory buffer.

Listing 5.7: Extract of the user-space program.

```
int file_desc = open("/dev/cgra_dma", O_RDWR);
...
mmap_ptr = mmap(NULL, CGRA_DATA_REGION_SIZE, PROT_READ | PROT_WRITE,
    MAP_SHARED, file_desc, 0);
...
// Write CGRA configuration
memcpy((mmap_ptr + CONFIG_OFFSET), cgra_kernel, cgra_kernel_size_words*
    sizeof(uint32_t));
// Write input data
memcpy((mmap_ptr+INPUT_OFFSET), input_data, DATA_SIZE*sizeof(uint32_t));

// Configure DMA
CGRA_control_t cgra_ctrl = {0};
cgra_ctrl.conf_offs = CONFIG_OFFSET;
cgra_ctrl.conf_count = cgra_kernel_size_words;
cgra_ctrl.in0_offs = INPUT_OFFSET;
cgra_ctrl.in0_count = ...
cgra_ctrl.in0_stride = ...
...
cgra_ctrl.out0_offs = OUTPUT_OFFSET;
cgra_ctrl.out0_count = ...

// Configure and execute
ioctl(file_desc, IOCTL_CGRA_CONTROL, &cgra_ctrl);
ioctl(file_desc, IOCTL_CGRA_CONFIG);
ioctl(file_desc, IOCTL_CGRA_EXEC);

// Read output data
memcpy(output_data, (mmap_ptr + OUTPUT_OFFSET), DATA_SIZE*sizeof(
    uint32_t));
```

Chapter 6

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This chapter includes resource usage and execution time metrics for the implemented design. A set of tasks is executed both in the CPU and with the aid of the CGRA accelerator, in bare-metal and under Linux. Results are later graphed and compared.

6.1 Resource Utilization Metrics

Synthesis was carried out for two configurations, allowing 24 and 10 outstanding transactions, respectively. The clock frequency was set to that of the CVA6 Development Platform, 50 MHz.

Resource usage by each module and resource type is gathered in Table 6.1 and Table 6.2, together with the percentage of the FPGA's available resources that are used. The DMA Interface, Crossbar, and Atomics modules are highlighted as the ones with the highest variation in resource utilization.

Table 6.1: Resource utilization for 24 outstanding transactions, with the XC7K325T-2FFG900C Kintex-7 FPGA.

	LUTs	FFs	BRAMs	DSPs
CVA6	47854	24725	36	27
CGRA	14078	9138	0	48
<u>DMA Interface</u>	<u>5838</u>	<u>8510</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>0</u>
ILA	3167	5487	103	0
<u>Crossbar</u>	<u>7234</u>	<u>7279</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>0</u>
<u>Atomics</u>	<u>10198</u>	<u>5837</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>0</u>
Peripherals & Other	24242	20701	13	0
Total Used	112611 (42.1 %)	81677 (20.0 %)	152 (34.2 %)	75 (8.9 %)

Table 6.2: Resource utilization for 10 outstanding transactions, with the XC7K325T-2FFG900C Kintex-7 FPGA.

	LUTs	FFs	BRAMs	DSPs
CVA6	47889	24724	36	27
CGRA	14072	9138	0	48
DMA Interface	4452	4529	0	0
ILA	3167	5487	103	0
Crossbar	6363	6663	0	0
Atomics	5052	2811	0	0
Peripherals & Other	24241	20701	13	0
Total Used	105236 (39.3 %)	74053 (18.2 %)	152 (34.2 %)	75 (8.9 %)

For easier comparison, Figure 6.1 and Figure 6.2 graph the data presented in the previous tables. Comparing both figures shows how the number of LUTs and FFs decreases when the number of outstanding transactions is reduced. This decrease is due to the smaller FIFOs in the DMA interface and the smaller internal buffers needed to support the lower number of outstanding transactions in the Crossbar and Atomics modules.

The graphs also show how the CGRA is the largest module in terms of DSP blocks, followed by the CVA6 core. This is because each CGRA processing element has an arithmetic unit. Moreover, most BRAMs are used by the ILA to store signal traces.

Figure 6.1: Resource utilization for 24 outstanding transactions.

Figure 6.2: Resource utilization for 10 outstanding transactions.

6.2 Proposed Applications for Performance Evaluation

This section describes two test applications proposed in [3] for performance evaluation: ReLU, a one-shot kernel that admits unrolling, and 2D convolution, which requires a multi-shot kernel operation.

6.2.1 ReLU

ReLU is a function used in neural networks that takes a number as input, outputting the same number if the input is positive or zero if the input is negative. This application uses the comparator in the CGRA's PEs.

The low resource usage allows the unrolling of the operation, up to a factor of three, as shown in Figure 6.3. As noted before, in the case of the X-Heap CGRA implementation, multiple memory accesses could be performed at a time due to the use of banked memory with interleaved addressing. This is not the case for the current CVA6 implementation, which can, at most, perform one read and one write operation per cycle. Therefore, unrolling does not provide any performance gain, and may even be detrimental. The effect of unrolling will be explored in Subsection 6.3.

Figure 6.3: ReLU CGRA mapping [3].

6.2.2 2D convolution

Convolution is an operation that is useful in image processing. It involves, for each pixel, the addition of its value and those of the neighboring pixels, weighted by a convolution matrix. In this case, by performing the convolution of an image by a 3x3 matrix.

$$\text{Convolution Matrix} = \begin{pmatrix} f_0 & f_1 & f_2 \\ f_3 & f_4 & f_5 \\ f_6 & f_7 & f_8 \end{pmatrix}$$

A convolution operation using the CGRA can be carried out in three steps, each with a different CGRA configuration; thus, it is considered a "multi-shot" kernel, as mentioned in Section 2.7.

Figure 6.4 shows the two different CGRA configurations needed for this task. Figure 6.4(a), used for the first pass, multiplies and adds pixels of the input image by the top row of the convolution matrix, whose coefficients are included in the CGRA's configuration.

Figure 6.4(b) performs the same task for the second and third rows of the convolution matrix, adding the result to that of the previous pass. If the bottom two rows of the convolution matrix are identical, then the CGRA does not have to be reconfigured between the second and third passes.

Finally, Figure 6.5 depicts the input and output data ranges for each of the passes and how each three-pixel block of the input image affects a single pixel of the output image on each pass. Pixels on the border of the output image are discarded.

Figure 6.4: 2D convolution CGRA mapping.

Figure 6.5: 2D convolution implementation using the CGRA.

6.3 Execution Time Metrics

6.3.1 ReLU

The possibility of unrolling the ReLU operation was mentioned in the previous section. Unrolling an operation changes the memory access pattern as data is read and written at different, non-consecutive addresses. This results from data in different regions of memory being processed concurrently.

It has been observed that the DRAM memory controller allows significantly less write bandwidth under this access pattern. Execution times with unrolling by a factor of 1 and 2 are graphed in Figure 6.6, which shows that the latter increases execution time by a factor of 3.

A setting for the write round-robin arbiter has been added so that, by enabling it, output FIFOs are emptied completely instead of taking one word at a time from each FIFO. This cuts execution time in half (modified RR in Figure 6.6) and could be helpful for an application that generates multiple pieces of data. As for ReLU, in this case, unrolling by a factor of 1 is the fastest of the alternatives and the one with which further tests will be carried out.

Figure 6.6: ReLU. Effect of unrolling on execution time.

Execution time for the ReLU operation was evaluated under the following conditions:

- Using CPU alone or with the aid of the CGRA.
- With the CPU running a bare-metal program or a user process under Linux.
- Operating on 16 or 32 KB of data (8192 and 4096 32-bit words).
- With an FPGA configuration that allows 10 or 24 outstanding transactions.

For execution under Linux, an average of 10 executions is taken due to the variability in the execution time brought on by the operating system.

Figures 6.7 through 6.10 compare the execution time between the CPU alone and with the aid of the CGRA accelerator, running either in bare-metal or under Linux, for a given set of conditions.

The time needed to use the CGRA is broken up into execution, configuration loading, and setup. Setup involves setting the CGRA module's CSRs to the required values. In the case of execution under Linux, the previous items include the overhead of system calls to access the driver. Furthermore, the overhead of copying configuration and data to the shared buffer and retrieving output data from it is also considered. As noted in Chapter 5, this becomes necessary due to the virtual and physical address spaces.

For execution in bare-metal, it can be seen that the CGRA offers a 3.7x speed improvement over the CPU alone with 10 outstanding transactions, and of 8.7x with 24 outstanding transactions, with execution time dominating the total CGRA time for the tested data sizes. As a reference, the X-Heep microcontroller implementation achieved a speedup of 15.4x for this task, with 2048 32-bit words [3].

Under Linux, the CGRA offers a 2.1x speed improvement for 10 outstanding transactions and 2.2x for 24 transactions. The slight improvement with the increase in

outstanding transactions is due to CGRA time being dominated, in this case, by memory copy operations between the CGRA and the shared buffer. This reduces the effectiveness of the CGRA as an accelerator.

It is worth noting that memory copy operations not involving the shared buffer have been found to take the same amount of time as those that do. This is so because, as noted in Chapter 5, the shared buffer remains cached. Because of this, the driver flushes the data cache before returning control to the user-space process.

Figure 6.7: ReLU 16 kB, 10 outstanding transactions.

It has also been found that executing the same ReLU task with the CPU takes 5.5x more clock cycles when running under Linux than in bare-metal. This will be discussed further at the end of this chapter.

Figure 6.8: ReLU 32 kB, 10 outstanding transactions.

Figure 6.9: ReLU 16 kB, 24 outstanding transactions.

Figure 6.10: ReLU 32 kB, 24 outstanding transactions.

6.3.2 2D convolution

The execution time for the 2D convolution task is evaluated in the same way as in the ReLU task. In this case, the 2D convolution of 32x32 and 64x64 images is performed with a 3x3 convolution matrix.

As before, the task is executed with 10 and 24 outstanding transactions and is run either in bare-metal or under Linux, taking an average of 10 executions for the latter.

The results are graphed in Figures 6.11 through 6.14, which follow the same conventions as those of the preceding section.

In bare-metal, the CGRA offers a 0.5x speed improvement for 10 outstanding transactions and a 1.1x improvement for 24. These numbers, and the additional complexity required for using the accelerator for this multi-shot kernel task, make the setup unsuitable for accelerating this operation. The main limiting factor, as in the case of ReLU, is the available memory access bandwidth. Conversely, due to its multiple-master capability, the X-Heep implementation achieved a significant

speedup of 18.6x with 64x64 images.

Under Linux, the CGRA offers a 3.8x improvement for 10 outstanding transactions and 4.3x for 24. In this case, memory copy overhead is still a significant portion of the total time, but less so than with the ReLU task. This is so because the input image is copied once but used three times, one per pass.

The 2D convolution operation in software takes 4.9x more cycles under Linux than in baremetal, a similar number to the ReLU case.

Figure 6.11: Conv2D 32x32, 10 outstanding transactions.

Figure 6.12: Conv2D 64x64, 10 outstanding transactions.

Figure 6.13: Conv2D 32x32, 24 outstanding transactions.

Figure 6.14: Conv2D 64x64, 24 outstanding transactions.

6.4 On the Overhead of Linux

6.4.1 Time measurement procedure

Time measurements under Linux were performed with the `clock_gettime()` function [78], using the `CLOCK_MONOTONIC_RAW` clock ID. This means that `clock_gettime()` returns a measure of elapsed time derived directly from a hardware timer. This is the desired behavior when timing execution using the CGRA.

Execution time of the software implementations was also measured using `CLOCK_PROCESS_CPUTIME_ID`, which measures the CPU time consumed by the process. Results are 3% lower than the elapsed time, so the elapsed time measurements remain representative.

6.4.2 Overhead of the Linux implementation

In the previous section, it was noted that the software implementation of the ReLU task was 5.5x slower under Linux than in bare-metal, and 4.9x slower for the 2D convolution.

This overhead can be attributed to the Memory Management Unit being enabled for address translation; the slightly smaller overhead in the 2D convolution, to the higher utilization of the data cache by this task.

The same software tasks were executed in a dual-core ARM Cortex-A9 processor running at 650 MHz on a Pynq-Z1 development board. Execution times, both in bare-metal and under Linux, are recorded in Table 6.3. Linux overhead is 17 % for ReLU and 5 % for 2D convolution, lower due to the use of the data cache. These numbers are in line with the 15-30 % mentioned in the literature [79].

The relatively low system clock frequency of 50 MHz may explain the higher overhead of the CVA6 FPGA implementation.

Table 6.3: Execution time in baremetal and under Linux on a 650 MHz dual-core Arm Cortex-A9.

	ReLU (32 KB)	2D convolution (32x32 image)
Baremetal	266 us	184 us
Linux (10 avgs.)	313 us	194 us

Chapter 7

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

7.1 Conclusions

This work has demonstrated the integration of a CGRA accelerator in an SoC platform with a RISC-V host processor. As outlined in the objectives, a suitable state-of-the-art RISC-V processor and its development platform, the CVA6 Development Platform, were selected. This platform was then studied and started in an FPGA development board available at CEI, generating documentation on the process, aiming to ease future developments.

The STRELA CGRA was introduced, and a module including a novel DMA interface was developed for the integration of the CGRA in the selected platform. This DMA interface replaces the multiple memory nodes, each acting as an independent master, that were present on the previous X-Heep microcontroller STRELA implementation.

Finally, a Linux kernel module was written to enable the use of the accelerator from within Linux, and performance was evaluated both in a bare-metal and in a Linux context.

From the developments in this work and the associated experimental results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

The CVA6 STRELA implementation provides 1.7x and 17x less baremetal speedup than the X-Heep implementation for the ReLU and 2D convolution tasks. Although the two implementations are not directly comparable due to the different nature of the host processors (application-class and microcontroller-class), it is clear that the memory access bandwidth is limiting the performance of the CGRA accelerator in the CVA6 implementation. This results in not taking full advantage of the parallel processing capability of the CGRA.

It has been found that increasing the number of outstanding transactions slightly increases resource utilization while significantly improving performance. Thus, it is worth increasing this number up to the memory latency.

Working in a Linux context incurs significant overhead, owing to address translation and memory copy operations to a shared memory buffer. The overhead of address translation is higher than expected in the FPGA emulation of the CVA6 development platform. This aspect needs to be investigated further.

The CVA6 development platform has complex simulation and synthesis flows and lacks complete documentation. This has resulted in a challenging platform and tool setup. On the other hand, the project has an active user community, which is a positive aspect.

7.2 Future Work

As noted in Chapter 1, this work is a first step towards developing an edge node based on RISC-V for the MYRTUS project. Further work would involve improving performance, connecting the node to a network, and the developments needed to target the MYRTUS project's healthcare and mobility use cases.

Although the CVA6 Development Platform was used in this work, Cheshire [80] was presented as an alternative in Section 2.6. This platform includes a last-level cache between DRAM and the SoC's interconnect and has potentially simpler simulation and synthesis flows, as opposed to the CVA6 development platform, which is geared towards verification of the processor itself. Future work may involve the evaluation of this platform.

As outlined in Section 4.3, the developed DMA interface does not make full use of the 64-bit wide interconnect when accessing contiguous memory. A possible next step would be adding additional hardware to improve performance in this scenario.

A further approach to improve memory access bandwidth could be to provide an accelerator cache that allowed multiple simultaneous accesses, such as the Tightly-Coupled Data Memory used in [40] (see Subsection 2.4.5). This memory works much in the same way as X-Heep's interleaved addressing.

Another topic to be explored is the configuration of the CGRA accelerator and the DMA transfers using custom instructions, potentially speeding up these operations.

Chapter 8

PLANNING, BUDGET AND IMPACT

8.1 Socioeconomic and Environmental Impact

As the work presented here is the first step in developing an edge node, socioeconomic and environmental impacts are difficult to quantify, as the primary factors are the specifics of the use case and the materials, construction, and life-cycle of future devices.

8.2 Legal and Ethical Concerns

This work uses IP published under open-source licenses such as Solderpad, BSD-3, and Apache-2.0. The terms of these licenses would have to be considered upon redistribution of any work derived from, or that makes use of, the said IP.

Concerns about information privacy could arise regarding the MYRTUS use cases of healthcare and mobility. Specific details pertain to actual implementation, yet moving computing effort from the cloud to the edge or fog has advantages from a privacy standpoint.

8.3 Contribution to UN's Sustainable Development Goals

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) set by the United Nations in 2015 [12] target problems related to poverty, hunger, health, resources, and the environment, among others. Figure 8.1 summarizes the 17 goals.

Figure 8.1: UN's sustainable development goals [12].

This work targets the "industry, innovation, and infrastructure" goal primarily. Yet, the MYRTUS project's healthcare and mobility use cases contribute to the "good health and well-being" and "sustainable cities and communities" goals, respectively.

In addition, the techniques developed as part of the MYRTUS project and the Internet of Things could have applications in fields such as energy, wildlife, and climate.

8.4 Planning and Budget

8.4.1 Planning

Figure 8.2 shows the dates and durations of the tasks carried out as part of this work, including the state-of-the-art, hardware development and testing, and report writing. Empty slots in January and May correspond to exam periods.

Figure 8.2: Gantt chart of this work.

8.4.2 Budget

Table 8.1 shows a simplified budget for this work, including student and supervisor work hours, used hardware, and software licenses.

Table 8.1: Budget for this work.

Item	Unit Cost (€)	Quantity	Subtotal (€)
Student work	10/h	800	8000
Supervisor work	50/h	50	2500
KC705 development board	2538	1	2538
Computer	600	1	600
Vivado License	1300/50 units	1	26
Total			13664

Bibliography

- [1] Danylo Khalyeyev, Tomas Bureš, and Petr Hnětynka. Towards characterization of edge-cloud continuum. In *European Conference on Software Architecture*, pages 215–230. Springer, 2022.
- [2] MYRTUS European project proposal. Part B: Technical description, 2023.
- [3] Daniel Vazquez, Jose Miranda, Alfonso Rodriguez, Andres Otero, Pascuale Davide Schiavone, and David Atienza. STRELA: STReaming ELAstic CGRA Accelerator for Embedded Systems. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2404.12503*, 2024.
- [4] Cheshire user manual: Architecture. <https://pulp-platform.github.io/cheshire/um/arch/>.
- [5] Carfield user manual: Architecture. <https://pulp-platform.github.io/carfield/um/arch/>.
- [6] OpenHW Group CVA6 Documentation: CVA6 APU. https://docs.openhwgroup.org/projects/cva6-user-manual/05_cva6_apu/index.html.
- [7] Occamy reference manual: System Components Description. https://pulp-platform.github.io/occamy/rm/3_system_components.html.
- [8] Jonathan Balkind, Michael McKeown, Yaosheng Fu, Tri Nguyen, Yanqi Zhou, Alexey Lavrov, Mohammad Shahrads, Adi Fuchs, Samuel Payne, Xiaohua Liang, et al. Openpiton: An open source manycore research framework. *ACM SIGPLAN Notices*, 51(4):217–232, 2016.
- [9] Simone Machetti, Pasquale Davide Schiavone, Thomas Christoph Müller, Miguel Peón-Quirós, and David Atienza. X-heep: An open-source, configurable and extendible risc-v microcontroller for the exploration of ultra-low-power edge accelerators. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.05548*, 2024.
- [10] ARM. AMBA AXI and ACE Protocol Specification Version E. <https://developer.arm.com/documentation/ih10022/e/?lang=en>.
- [11] Daniel E. Gisselquist. Building a basic AXI Master. <https://zipcpu.com/blog/2020/03/23/wbm2axisp.html>, 2020.
- [12] United Nations. The 17 sustainable development goals. <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>, 2024.
- [13] Juan Granja. Evaluation of Open-Source RISC-V Platforms for the Cloud-Edge Continuum. June 2024.
- [14] MYRTUS Use-case: Smart Mobility and Virtual Telerehabilitation. <https://myrtus-project.eu/use-case/>, 2024.
- [15] Open Source Hardware & Software Working Group. Recommendations and roadmap for European sovereignty on open source hardware, software and RISC-V Technologies. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/recommendations-and-roadmap-european-sovereignty-open-source-hardware-software-and-risc-v>, 2023.

-
- [16] Mark Wijtvliet, Luc Waeijen, and Henk Corporaal. Coarse grained reconfigurable architectures in the past 25 years: Overview and classification. In *2016 International Conference on Embedded Computer Systems: Architectures, Modeling and Simulation (SAMOS)*, pages 235–244. IEEE, 2016.
- [17] Martin A. Enderwitz Louise H. Crockett, Ross A. Elliot and Robert W. Stewart. *The Zynq Book*. Strathclyde Academic Media, 1 edition, 2014.
- [18] RISC-V International. The RISC-V Instruction Set Manual Volume I. Version 20240411. <https://riscv.org/technical/specifications/>, 2024.
- [19] John L. Hennessy David A. Patterson. *Computer Organization and Design*. Morgan Kaufmann, 5 edition, 2014.
- [20] OpenHW Group About Us page. <https://www.openhwgroup.org/about-us/>, 2024.
- [21] LowRISC About Us Page. <https://lowrisc.org/about-us/>, 2024.
- [22] Florian Zaruba. *Energy-Efficient High-Performance Computing*. Doctoral dissertation, ETH Zürich, 2021.
- [23] CVA6 GitHub Repository. <https://github.com/openhwgroup/cva6>.
- [24] Jérôme Quévremont. An Open-Source Application Core:CVA6 from the OpenHW Group. <https://open-src-soc.org/2022-05/media/slides/4th-RISC-V-Meeting-2022-05-04-14h55-J%C3%A9r%C3%B4me-Qu%C3%A9vremont.pdf>, 2022.
- [25] CV32E40P GitHub Repository. <https://github.com/openhwgroup/cv32e40p>.
- [26] Pulpino GitHub Repository. <https://github.com/pulp-platform/pulpino>.
- [27] Ibex GitHub Repository. <https://github.com/lowRISC/ibex>.
- [28] Florian Zaruba, Fabian Schuiki, Torsten Hoefler, and Luca Benini. Snitch: A tiny pseudo dual-issue processor for area and energy efficient execution of floating-point intensive workloads. *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 70(11):1845–1860, 2020.
- [29] Krste Asanovic, Rimas Avizienis, Jonathan Bachrach, Scott Beamer, David Biancolin, Christopher Celio, Henry Cook, Daniel Dabbelt, John Hauser, Adam Izraelevitz, et al. The rocket chip generator. *EECS Department, University of California, Berkeley, Tech. Rep. UCB/EECS-2016-17*, 4:6-2, 2016.
- [30] Daniel Petrisko, Farzam Gilani, Mark Wyse, Dai Cheol Jung, Scott Davidson, Paul Gao, Chun Zhao, Zahra Azad, Sadullah Canakci, Bandhav Veluri, et al. Blackparrot: An agile open-source risc-v multicore for accelerator socs. *IEEE Micro*, 40(4):93–102, 2020.
- [31] Frontgrade Gaisler AB. Noel-v product page. <https://www.gaisler.com/index.php/products/processors/noel-v>.
- [32] Frontgrade Gaisler AB. Grlib ip core user’s manual. <https://www.gaisler.com/products/grlib/grip.pdf>, 2024.
- [33] OpenHW Group. Core-V eXtension interface (CV-X-IF). <https://docs.openhwgroup.org/projects/openhw-group-core-v-xif/>, 2024.
- [34] Davide Pala. *Design and programming of a coprocessor for a RISC-V architecture*. PhD thesis, Politecnico di Torino, 2017.
- [35] Natalie Enright Jerger, Tushar Krishna, and Li-Shiuan Peh. *On-chip networks*. Springer Nature, 2022.
- [36] Alessandro Ottaviano et al. Cheshire: A lightweight, linux-capable risc-v host platform for domain-specific accelerator plug-in, 2023.

-
- [37] Angelo Garofalo. Carfield: An Open-Research Platform for Safety, Resilient and Predictable Systems. https://pulp-platform.org/docs/dac2023/Carfield_SSH_SoC_DAC23_v2_pdf.pdf, 2023.
- [38] Michael Rogenmoser, Yvan Tortorella, Davide Rossi, Francesco Conti, and Luca Benini. Hybrid modular redundancy: Exploring modular redundancy approaches in RISC-V multi-core computing clusters for reliable processing in space. *ACM Transactions on Cyber-Physical Systems*, 2023.
- [39] Occamy: A 432-core, Multi-TFLOPs RISC-V-Based 2.5D Chiplet System for Ultra-Efficient (Mini-)Floating-Point Computation. <https://pulp-platform.org/occamy/>.
- [40] Andreas Kurth, Björn Forsberg, and Luca Benini. Herov2: Full-stack open-source research platform for heterogeneous computing. *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems*, 33(12):4368–4382, 2022.
- [41] Luca Benini, Frank K. Gürkaynak. Working with RISC-V. Part 3 of 4 : PULP concepts. https://pulp-platform.org/docs/hipeac/acaces2020/03_PULP_Concepts.pdf, 2020.
- [42] Heterogeneous Research Platform (HERO) GitHub Repository. <https://github.com/pulp-platform/hero>.
- [43] Alon Amid, David Biancolin, Abraham Gonzalez, Daniel Grubb, Sagar Karandikar, Harrison Liew, Albert Magyar, Howard Mao, Albert Ou, Nathan Pemberton, et al. Chipyard: Integrated design, simulation, and implementation framework for custom socs. *IEEE Micro*, 40(4):10–21, 2020.
- [44] Joseph Zuckerman, Paolo Mantovani, Davide Giri, and Luca P Carloni. Enabling heterogeneous, multicore soc research with risc-v and esp. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2206.01901*, 2022.
- [45] Joseph Zuckerman et al. ESP GitHub repository: Tools for design automation and external communication with an ESP SoC. <https://github.com/sld-columbia/esp/tree/main/tools>, 2024.
- [46] Jonathan Balkind, Ting-Jung Chang, Paul J Jackson, Georgios Tziantzioulis, Ang Li, Fei Gao, Alexey Lavrov, Grigory Chirkov, Jinzheng Tu, Mohammad Shahrad, et al. Openpiton at 5: A nexus for open and agile hardware design. *IEEE Micro*, 40(4):22–31, 2020.
- [47] Princeton University. OpenPiton GitHub Repository. <https://github.com/PrincetonUniversity/openpiton>.
- [48] Jonathan Balkind, Katie Lim, Michael Schaffner, Fei Gao, Grigory Chirkov, Ang Li, Alexey Lavrov, Tri M Nguyen, Yaosheng Fu, Florian Zaruba, et al. Byoc: a "bring your own core" framework for heterogeneous-isa research. In *Proceedings of the Twenty-Fifth International Conference on Architectural Support for Programming Languages and Operating Systems*, pages 699–714, 2020.
- [49] Zahra Azad. *On designing hardware accelerator-based systems: interfaces, taxes and benefits*. PhD thesis, Boston University, 2023.
- [50] Verilator SystemVerilog Simulator. <https://www.veripool.org/verilator/>, 2024.
- [51] Verilator GitHub repository. <https://github.com/verilator/verilator>, 2024.
- [52] Verilator Documentation: Installation Guide. <https://verilator.org/guide/latest/install.html#git-quick-install>, 2024.
- [53] Verilator Revision History: Version 5.002 2022-10-29. <https://verilator.org/guide/latest/changes.html#verilator-5-002-2022-10-29>, 2024.
- [54] Wilson Snyder. Verilator Release 5.026 Manual. https://www.veripool.org/ftp/verilator_doc.pdf, 2024.

-
- [55] About GitHub and Git. <https://docs.github.com/en/get-started/start-your-journey/about-github-and-git>.
- [56] Spike RISC-V ISA Simulator. <https://github.com/riscv-software-src/riscv-isa-sim>, 2024.
- [57] PULP Platform Repositories. <https://github.com/pulp-platform>, 2024.
- [58] Verilator doesn't stdout Hello CVA6! <https://github.com/openhwgroup/cva6/issues/748>, 2024.
- [59] Ethan Sifferman. Architecture Labs with CVA6. <https://github.com/sifferman/labs-with-cva6>, 2024.
- [60] Juan Granja. Debugging CVA6 APU on a KC705 board. <https://github.com/openhwgroup/cva6/issues/1803#issuecomment-2003829865>.
- [61] Dominic Rath. Open On-Chip Debugger. <https://openocd.org/pages/about.html>.
- [62] Xilinx. AMD Kintex7 FPGA KC705 Evaluation Kit. <https://www.xilinx.com/products/boards-and-kits/ek-k7-kc705-g.html>, 2024.
- [63] Digilent. Digilent Genesys 2 Board. <https://digilent.com/reference/programmable-logic/genesys-2/start>, 2024.
- [64] Xilinx. BSCANE 2. Vivado Design Suite 7 Series FPGA and Zynq-7000 SoC Libraries Guide. <https://docs.amd.com/r/2021.1-English/ug953-vivado-7series-libraries/BSCANE2>, 2024.
- [65] RISC-V Debug Support for various Cores. <https://github.com/pulp-platform/riscv-dbg>, 2024.
- [66] X-Heep BSCANE 2 OpenOCD Script. <https://github.com/esl-epfl/x-heep/blob/main/tb/core-v-mini-mcu-pynq-z2-bscan.cfg>, 2024.
- [67] CVA6 GitHub Repository/.../csr_regfile.sv: CSR_DCACHE. https://github.com/openhwgroup/cva6/blob/9ecdaa140862748ee7f94f82cf41467f54ea195a/core/csr_regfile.sv#L556.
- [68] The RISC-V Instruction Set Manual for CV32A65X: Volume II: Privileged Architecture. https://cva6.readthedocs.io/en/latest/04_cv32a65x/riscv/priv.html#_privilege_levels, 2024.
- [69] Norbert Kremeris. Verilator Pt.2: Basics of SystemVerilog verification using C++. <https://zipcpu.com/blog/2020/03/23/wbm2axisp.html>, 2021.
- [70] OpenHW Group cva6-sdk GitHub repository. <https://github.com/openhwgroup/cva6-sdk>, 2024.
- [71] Buildroot Embedded Linux System Generation Tool. <https://buildroot.org/>, 2024.
- [72] Denys Vlasenko. BusyBox: The Swiss Army Knife of Embedded Linux. <https://www.busybox.net/about.html>, 2024.
- [73] Jonathan Corbet, Alessandro Rubini, and Greg Kroah-Hartman. *Linux Device Drivers*. O'Reilly, third edition, February 2005.
- [74] Peter Jay Salzman, Michael Burian, Ori Pomerantz, Bob Mottram, and Jim Huang. The Linux Kernel Module Programming Guide. <https://sysprog21.github.io/lkmpg/>, 2024.
- [75] Alfonso Rodriguez. ARTICo³ kernel module. <https://github.com/des-cei/artico3/tree/master/linux/drivers/artico3>, 2019.
- [76] dma_alloc_coherent crashes kernel module. <https://stackoverflow.com/questions/72956071/dma-alloc-coherent-crashes-kernel-module>, 2022.

-
- [77] `dma_alloc_coherent` crashes kernel module. <https://stackoverflow.com/questions/72956071/dma-alloc-coherent-crashes-kernel-module>, 2022.
- [78] Linux manual pages - `clock_gettime`. https://man7.org/linux/man-pages/man2/clock_gettime.2.html, 2024.
- [79] Guilherme Cox and Abhishek Bhattacharjee. Efficient address translation for architectures with multiple page sizes. *ACM SIGPLAN Notices*, 52(4):435–448, 2017.
- [80] Cheshire github repository. <https://github.com/pulp-platform/cheshire>.

